

Master Graduate Degree Program STEEM (Energy Environment : Science Technology & Management)

Master's Thesis Operating photovoltaic power plants : Big data and Modeling

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Preface and Acknowledgements

I spent five months and half period, from 16 April to 19 September 2018, as a trainee at the Group of electrical engineering in Paris (GeePs), a laboratory of CentraleSupélec, in Gif sur Yvette, France. This internship project is a part of my 2-year master program which I conduct at Ecole Polytechnique, in Palaiseau, France.

Before I explain my experience and my work, I would like to thank the department of PHEMADIC who gave me the opportunity to work there. I found this traineeship extremely useful. My experience in any kind of programming was quite limited upon arrival in GeePs ; however, during my time there I developed my skills and managed to build up a fairly MATLAB program for diverse purposes (data processing, filtering, modeling and simulating). I did not only gain technical knowledge but more importantly, I had a great chance to sharpen my skills in a professional working environment. I have been trained and practiced my communication skills through giving presentations, discussing with the supervisors. This internship was a first step to discover what the research implies, how a laboratory is functioning at an everyday schedule level. This was an opportunity to confront different opinions about research and the perspectives on how to practice this profession.

First and foremost I am using this opportunity to express my deepest appreciation to Mme Anne MIGAN, my direct supervisor at GeePs, for providing me the opportunity to study such an interesting topic about the operation of PV power plant and, moreover for her valuable suggestions and advices whenever needed. Furthermore, she usually gave me a chance to participate in seminars, conferences such as “La Journée Scientifique SIRTA 2018” and “La journée des doctorants de Centrale Supélec”. I had a great time to learn from PhD students. Thank you for being a great internship tutor, providing excellent advices and guiding regarding this work during the whole period of the internship. Thank you for your patience, your help, your welcome and your support during the execution of this master’s thesis.

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Finally, I am grateful to my parents and my brother for their love, support, sacrifices over the past years and the strength and determination they gave me during my academic path and my staying in Paris. Your help was invaluable.

Abstract :

The framework of this study is the performance assessment of grid-connected photovoltaic modules in real outdoor operating conditions. The photovoltaic (PV) power plant is located on the roof of building of IUT (University Institute of Technology) in Cachan, France. The system is equipped with 8 polycrystallines (poly-Si) and 16 amorphous silicon (a-Si) modules connected in series.

The set of data visualized and analyzed in this study has been systematically acquired from 2011 to 2016 by means of a dedicated monitoring system composed by weather sensors, 2 inverters (one for each technology) and 2 dataloggers (one for each technology) that gather all the data. A **processing methodology** was applied to appropriately import, test, visualize and analyze the data to interpretate the yearlong evolution of the PV installation, separating the variability of environmental conditions (Irradiance and ambient temperature) from the variability of electrical components (AC & DC voltage, and AC power). The most limitation is that we have lack of available electrical measurements at DC side (power and current) for both technologies and lack of available atmospheric data measurements for polycrystallines modules, which were recovered from the climatic measurements of amorphous modules. The plots of climatic data as a function of time were similar for both technologies, which confirm that the data recovery has been done successfully, however, some abnormal points located above and below the irradiance-power straight line show that there is lags between the time that the datalogger records the irradiance and ambient temperature measurements from a-Si modules and the time when it registers power values from the inverter connected to poly-Si modules. Data cleaning has been done to avoid this synchronization but we still have this problem for 2014-2015-2016. This problem is mentioned in the report. Afterwards, the original 15-min measurements were averaged over 1h, and datasets were used to develop different simulation models, useful for assessing the deviation from the measures.

For this research work, the power output at the AC side of the installed PV systems was modeled by using three different **modeling approaches**: Electrical Model (Single-Diode-Model SDM), Evans Model and Empirical Model (Photovoltaic for Utility-Scale Applications PVUSA). The models estimate the production using the measured solar irradiance G and PV module temperature T_{mod} calculated from the measurements of ambient temperature T_{amb} and irradiance G by **the Nominal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT) Model**.

Concerning the three models, the power output of each model depends on **PV module parameters**. To obtain these parameters, different conditions of simulation were used. In each model, we validate our results by studying different cases and by comparing the values obtained with the values found in bibliography or provided by the manufacturer.

For the **electrical model**, we chose the Single Diode Model (SDM). First we started with the simplified SDM model with 4 parameters that neglects the shunt resistance assuming it as infinite value and then we chose to work with 5 parameters model, which is more accurate. By knowing the short-circuit (SC) point, the open circuit (OC) point, the Maximum power point (MPP) and the slope of the I-V curve and by using the datasheets and the outdoor data set (solar irradiance G and module temperature T_{mod}), analytical calculations can be made to determine the initial values to solve the system of non-linear equations numerically. Comparing with the datasheets at STC, the accuracy of the results (of SDM-5 parameters) seems to be good, with a relative error (RE) less than 1% for polycrystalline and less than 7% for amorphous in term of power, current and voltage. The principal advantage of this model is that, contrary to the other models, it can compute the I-V & P-V curves and know the maximum power point at each operating point. Moreover, we don't need historical data to make regressions techniques to extract the parameters of the models, only datasheets parameters and data of operating conditions (G, T_{mod}).

Afterwards, we simulated the I-V & P-V curves by varying the irradiance and keeping the module temperature constant and vice versa, and finally we validate the model by comparing the simulated values of open circuit voltage $V_{oc,sim}$ and short circuit current $I_{sc,sim}$ to those calculated. We found a good agreement with an average relative error less than 1% for both technologies except the case of $V_{oc,sim}$ for amorphous, which drops drastically with the module temperature (RE is less than 12%).

The second approach is **Evans Model** that depends on 3 parameters and based on datasheet parameters, solar irradiance and module temperature, like the electrical model. First, different tests have been introduced in order to filter data to see the effect of high irradiance and high module temperature. Afterwards, we used linear regression to get these parameters. Then we validate the model using the fitted coefficients by comparing the results with the values given by the manufacturer and found in the literature. We found a good agreement, and some variations can be explained by the fact that the parameters given by the manufacturer (at Standart Test Conditions STC) are not suited to the outdoor conditions (G, T_{mod}).

The third approach is the **Empirical Model (PVUSA)** that depends also on 3 parameters and based exclusively on atmospheric data (solar irradiance and ambient temperature). The parameters of this model are extracted by filtering the constant values of ambient temperature and then of irradiance. By using linear and multiple regression we obtain these parameters. Then we validate the model by comparing the values of the fitted coefficients with the constants found in the datasheets. We found that the values are not far from each other, with RE less than 1%.

The parameters extracted of each model are determined only for the first year of the operation and will be fixed for the coming years. The detailed description of the PV module parameters extraction is shown in the chapter 4 of the report.

Results of the AC power simulated as a function of the AC power measured show that for **poly-si modules and amorphous modules**, the Evans and PVUSA models studied agree with measurements in the first year of operation (2011), in which the parameters extraction has been done, regardless of irradiance and ambient temperature, which confirm that the extraction of the parameters has been done successfully, which validate the Evans & PVUSA models. For SDM-5parameters, the model agree with measurements only for poly-si modules regardless of G and T_{amb} . However, it doesn't agree for amorphous, we found a gap at high G and T_{amb} . It was concluded that it is problem in the ideality factor of amorphous which is found high, when we tested with another value, the model works well. Hence this is not convenient for us to make further analysis. It was concluded that the 3 models agree with measurements.

It's important to note that **Evans and Empirical models simulate the production at AC side** since the regression to get the parameters used the measurements at the AC side, which means that the inverter efficiency is assumed constant. However, the SDM with 5 parameters provides only the output power at the DC side. Therefore, we used inverter model of moderate complexity to **obtain the inverter efficiency** so that we can simulate the production at the AC side. The inverter efficiency is also determined only for the first year of the operation and will be fixed for the coming years.

The simulation approaches will be used to study **the fault diagnosis techniques** of possible failure sources in the PV panels leading to total or partial loss of productivity. We proposed different methods and algorithms.

The first method "Comparison between the measured power and the modeled one" (CMM) consists on comparing the simulated production **at AC side** of the 3 models against the outdoor-measured annual AC power over the period of evaluation (6years from 2011 to 2016) for amorphous and only in 2011-2012 and 2013 for poly-si, corresponding to the years when we don't have synchronization troubles. The comparison was made by using statistical indicators to keep track of the system's long-term performance, by calculating and analyzing the deviations in each year of operation, for different seasons of the year 2012 for which we have enough data points and we discussed the effect of irradiance and ambient temperature on these deviations.

Results show that, for **poly-Si modules**, we have quite small deviations all the years (RMAE=5-9%) with the 3 models. However, for **amorphous** we have small errors in 2011-2012-2016 (around 4-6% for Evans and SDM models and 12-17% with PVUSA model); the high values of deviations are found in 2013-2014-2016 (around 12-19% for Evans and SDM models and 28-36% for PVUSA model). It was concluded that the parameters extraction has been done successfully for poly-Si because the statistical errors are small for the 3 models. For amorphous, we have some deviations especially in 2014-2015 and the highest deviation is found for PVUSA. It doesn't allow, however, drawing conclusions that there is faulty functioning in 2014-2015 or there is problem in the parameters extraction. All the models indicate that we have more deviations in winter and autumn (more deviation of amorphous in autumn and more deviation of poly in winter) and less deviation in spring and summer. Overall, all the models agree with measurements all the years and regardless of G and T_{amb} which confirm that the identification parameters results of the 3 models developed has been done successfully which validate the models to start the faults diagnosis techniques.

After the calculation of deviations between measures and models at AC side, we proposed **two faults detection algorithms**. The **first faults detection algorithm** is based on the evaluation of **the normal operation limits calculated by the performance index** (the ratio between the measured and modeled AC power). The **second fault detection algorithm** at AC side is based on **power error**. These algorithms used the 3 models developed (SDM-5parameters; Evans and PVUSA models) and were tested using data in the actual fault free operation in the period when we don't have synchronization troubles (in 2011-2012-2013 for poly-Si and all the years from 2011 to 2016 for amorphous).

The **second method** was focused on the malfunctions **at DC side**. There are different algorithms: **one fault detection algorithm** based on the Power Losses Analysis (PLA), especially the **capture losses** (that take into account the losses due to high temperature and due to faulty operation such as faulty strings; short circuited modules, partial shadowing, low irradiance losses); **three fault identification algorithms** based on the current and voltage, **the second algorithm** is based on the **current and voltage errors** and the third one is based on the **current and voltage indicators**.

The detection algorithms determine if the PV installation is in normal or faulty operation and the identification algorithms determine the kind of faults that is carried out. These algorithms at DC side used only the SDM with 5 parameters extracted because it's the only one that provides the simulated current and the voltage at DC side. And we used the simulated inverter efficiency to convert the measurements from AC to DC. In all the algorithms, for detection and identification of faults, at AC or DC side, we fixed boundaries using standard deviation and thresholds found in the literature. These thresholds are calculated only for the first year of operation and are fixed for the rest period of evaluation. Different simulations were done to check if each parameter of each algorithm does not exceed the defined thresholds to decide whether to trigger the alarm or not.

We implemented these algorithms to the actual free fault operation. The two faults detection algorithms at AC side emits "faulty operation" all the years for both technologies using the 3 models. Moreover the graphs of normal operation limits show that some periods of time corresponding to the beginning and the end of each year, the power ratio and the power error don't lie inside the thresholds established. Overall, both algorithms appear accurate because they emit an alarm "normal operation" almost all the time after evaluating the actual free fault data.

At the DC side, after evaluating the actual free fault data, it was concluded from the faults identification algorithms that there is a problem in voltage and current which means partial shading, ground fault, line to line, ageing, MPPT error fault.

To verify the relevance of these algorithms at AC & DC sides that were studied in the actual free-fault operation, we injected faults in measurements. The period chosen for this study is the year 2011 for poly-Si and the year 2016 for amorphous, because we have enough data in these years. The main focus is on short-circuited modules because it's the common fault in PV system. We assumed that one module is short-circuited. Then, we simulated the PV installation with faulty state and tested the proposed algorithms. The PV system performance ratio (PR) and statistical indicators were used to see the difference before and after injection of faults. The algorithms emit the same faults «partial shading» which means problem in voltage and current even we simulate short circuit module (problem only in voltage). It was concluded that we need the correct thresholds so that the algorithms could properly work as we expected. Specific knowledge on the effect of faults on current and voltage is also essential to program our algorithm to emit the right alarm. It avoids chances of false or missed faults diagnosis. Therefore, we can't draw conclusions about the accuracy of these algorithms.

After that, we studied the impact of short-circuit module on performance ratio (PR) and statistical errors. We found less PR and more deviation after the simulation of the PV installation in faulty state. We studied the impact of short-circuited module on output power and output voltage. We obtain minimal impact on amorphous, it's evident that 1/16 module is short-circuited has less impact than 1/8 module short-circuited, which lead us to conclude that the bigger the PV system, the lower is the impact of a fault on the output power.

Keywords : amorphous and polycrystalline silicon photovoltaic modules; outdoor measurements; data processing, MATLAB programming; graphical analysis; non-linear equations; Modeling; Simulation; Flowcharts; single-diode model; I-V and P-V characteristics; Evans Model; Empirical Model; parameters extraction, Regression; fitted-coefficient; datasheet parameters; efficiency; Statistical indicators; fault diagnosis algorithms, faults detection, faults identification, normal operation, short-circuited modules, faulty state.

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List of Abbreviations

<p>AM : Air Mass (A) : Ampere α: the ideality factor of the junction P-N AC : Alternating current a-Si : Amorphous silicon PV modules CMM: Comparison between the measures and the models (C) : Colomb (°C) : degree DC : Direct current (eV): electron Volt E_g: Bandgap energy (eV) FF : fill factor GeePs : Group of electrical engineering in Paris G: Solar irradiance measured (W/m^2) (h) : hour I-V : Current-Voltage curve $I_{sc,cal}$: Short-circuit current calculated at given (G, T_{mod}) in (A) $I_{sc,a}$: The short-circuit current of the PV array (A) $I_{mpp, sim}$: Maximum power point current simulated at the DC side (A) $I_{mpp, STC}$: Maximum power point current of the PV module at STC (A) I: The output current of PV module (A) I_{ph}: The current generated by the incident light (A) I_d: Current through the diode (A) I_0: The saturated reverse current or leakage current (A) I_{sh}: Shunt current due to shunt resistor branch (A) $I_{sc, STC}$: Short-circuit current of the PV module at STC (A) $I_{sc, sim}$: Short-circuit current simulated (A) Inv : Inverter IUT : University Institute of Technology IEA : International Energy Agency (J) : Joule (K) : Kelvin K_i: Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current (%/K) converted to (A/K) K_v: Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage (%/K) converted to (V/K) $K_{p, STC}$: the temperature coefficient of the PV modules at STC (%/K) converted to (K^{-1}). $K_{p, fit}$: the temperature coefficient fitted of the PV modules (K^{-1}). k: Boltzmann's constant ($K=1.3806503 \times 10^{-23} J/K$) LMA: Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm L2S: Laboratory of Signals and Systems MPP : Maximum Power Point MPPT : Maximum Power Point Tracker NOCT : « Nominal Operating Cell Temperature » at $G_{NOCT} = 800W/m^2$; $T_{amb, NOCT} = 20^\circ C$; $AM = 1.5$ N: number of observations in the data « operating point(G, T_{mod}) » N_s: Number of cells in series in each PV module N_p: Number of cells in parallel in each PV module $N_{mod, s}$: Number of modules in series $N_{mod, p}$: Number of modules in parallel N_{mod}: Number of modules O&M : Operation & Maintenance OC : Open Circuit</p>	<p>PV : Photovoltaic P-V : Power-Voltage curve PR : Performance Ratio PR_{idx}: Performance Index (Output Ratio Power) Poly-Si : polycrystalline silicon PV modules PLA: Power Losses Analysis PVUSA: Photovoltaic for Utility-Scale Applications. Pt1000: Platinum Resistance thermometer $P_{mpp, STC}$: Maximum power point power or rated power output of the PV $P_{ac, meas}$: The measured power at the AC side(W) $\bar{P}_{ac, meas}$: is the average measured power of PV module (W) $P_{ac, sim}$: The simulated power at the AC side(W) $P_{mpp, sim}$: Maximum power point power simulated at the DC side q: The electron charge ($q=1.602 \times 10^{-19} C$) RE : Relative Error RMAE : Relative Mean Absolute Error (%) R_s: Series resistance of the module (Ω) R_p: Shunt/parallel resistance of the module (Ω) STC : « Standard Temperature Conditions » $G_{STC} = 1000W/m^2$; $T_{mod, STC} = 25^\circ C$; $AM=1.5$ SC : Short Circuit Si : Silicon SDM: Single-Diode-Model S_{Tot}: the total module area (m^2) S_u: the unit area of the PV module (m^2) T_{amb}: the ambient temperature measured ($^\circ C$) T_{mod}: is the module temperature calculated ($^\circ C$) using NOCT model Th: Threshold T_{NOCT} : Nominal operating cell temperature ($^\circ C$) provided by the manufacturer $TNR_{c, fs}$: threshold of faulty string fault $TNR_{v, scm}$: threshold of short-circuited module fault t: the monitoring time interval ($t=15min=0.25h$ or $1h$) (V) : Volt $V_{oc, STC}$: Open-circuit voltage of the PV module at STC (V) $V_{oc, sim}$: Open-circuit voltage simulated (V) $V_{mpp, STC}$: Maximum power point voltage of the PV module at STC (V) $V_{oc, cal}$: Open-circuit voltage calculated at given (G, T_{mod}) in (V) $V_{oc, a}$: The open-circuit voltage of the PV array (V) $V_{dc, meas}$: The DC voltage measured (V) $V_{ac, meas}$: The AC voltage measured (V) $V_{mpp, sim}$: Maximum power point voltage simulated at the DC side (V) V: Module output voltage (V) V_T: the thermal voltage of the module (V) (W) : Watt (Wh) : Watt hour (Ω): Ohm (%) : percentage $\eta_{inv, STC}$: inverter efficiency at STC $\eta_{inv, sim}$: inverter efficiency simulated $\eta_{PV, STC}$: the efficiency of the PV module at STC conditions γ_{fit}: the coefficient of irradiance fitted η_{fit}: the efficiency of the system (PV+inv) fitted δ and σ : Standard deviation</p>
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Chapter 1: Introduction

The following chapter contains a brief introduction to the current state of the photovoltaic energy. It describes the scope of the internship, the purpose of this study and gives a general outline of this thesis. Information on our PV installation, data generated by its operation and software used in this study are also included in this chapter.

1. Background of Photovoltaic power generation

Oil and gas fuels have been the main sources of energy for more than a century. Unfortunately, these sources have some acute problems: they are harmful to the environment, non-sustainable, insecure and their prices are soaring. Problems such as these led to increased interest in renewable energy sources such as wave, wind, and solar which are clean and sustainable in order to reduce the global warming phenomenon.

Among the renewable energies, the solar photovoltaic (PV) energy, given its maturity and ability to be quickly installed on the roofs of buildings, has been one of the most used research areas in electrical power generation, and its market has shown a rapid growth, especially in the area of distributed generation [1]. Solar power in France including overseas territories reached an installed capacity of 7165 MW by year-end 2016 generating 8790 GWh of power [2]. The solar power capacity is set to continue expanding with a target of around 18-20 GW installed by 2023 [3]. As solar energy becomes more accepted as a viable source of renewable energy, the implementation of PV monitoring system becomes a major concern. However, the number of monitored PV systems has not followed the same growing trend, as many PV plants.

As we know, under the different environment conditions, the efficiency of PV technologies decreases linearly with their operating temperature, compared to the efficiency under standard test conditions (STC). Hence, neither the peak power nor the efficiency at STC is representative of the mean operating performance: modules having equal STC powers may have very different long-term energy yields, even when located in the same place. Effects are observed during the use of these components in intermittent weather: rain, snow, dust, shock, and corrosion.

For this reason, designers need a flexible and reliable tool to continuously monitor and supervise remotely the components of the system. The implementation of this type of PV monitoring system allows us to process and analyse the great amount of registered data and to verify that the system delivers a suitable power by comparing with the expected values, calculated from the values of irradiance and ambient temperature measurements.

Often monitoring systems are built into inverter and are mainly designed to connect and disconnect from the utility during low or high voltage events. However, hidden defects or serious output power reduction due to some defects in PV modules can, in most cases, be ignored by these devices which can lead to the damage of PV modules or to a rise of safety hazards. Therefore, active monitoring and faults diagnosis algorithms can provide automatic control of PV systems, to analyze resulting information, and rapidly detect and identify any potential fault.

2. Internship description:

The internship takes place in GeePs, and carried out with the involvement of another laboratory: Laboratory of Signals and Systems (L2S). They are located in the south of Paris on the plateau of Moulon in Gif-sur-Yvette near CentraleSupélec. GeePs conducts mainly research in the field of electrical engineering including electromagnetic and electronic systems (their modeling and control) [4]. It is structured in three research departments: a materials division (PHEMADIC¹), an electromagnetism pole (PIEM²), and systems pole (ECo2³).

My internship was in PHEMADIC, and my direct supervisor is Mme Anne Migan, specialist in solar energy. Therefore, I had regular contact with her. I met Mme Migan almost every day when she is in the laboratory to present the work done or agreed to be done. I was also expected to periodically present advancement results in the form of progress reports and PowerPoint presentations realized in French, as well as to develop a final report summarizing all the results so that my co-supervisors Mr. Claude Delpha and Mr Demba Diallo followed on my work.

3. Internship objectives

As said in the introduction, It is essential to thoroughly study the performances of the modules under different conditions. There are several laboratories dedicated for studying PV modules and one example is the GeePs. The outdoor measurement field of the GeePs measures the performance of two PV modules technologies (polycrystallines and amorphous silicon) under real outdoor conditions over several months and years. The two PV technologies with their monitoring system are placed into the same location, on the roof of the building IUT in the area of Cachan in France, and they are connected to the grid.

The main objectives of this internship are to **a)** get familiar with all the data that are related to the operation of the two PV systems (one for each technology) from 2011 to 2016 **b)** develop a numerical scripts (in MATLAB) to process and apply quality control to the meteorological and electrical data generated by the operation of the PV installation in order to facilitate the interpretation, analyze the behavior of the inverters, quantify the degradation trends, and understand the abnormal values inherently present in real-life data, such an erroneous measurements and lagging between measurements **c)** develop different approaches to simulate the PV production using different models (electrical model SDM ; Evans Model ; and Empirical PVUSA Model). The objective is to compare the real instantaneous production with the modeled one using statistical tools to help find deviations and anomalies ; **d)** to

¹ PHEMADIC « Physical and Electronic of Materials, Devices, Interfaces and Contacts »

² PIEM « Physical and Engineering of Electromagnetism »

³ ECo2 « Energy, Electronic, Conception, Control »

develop fairly simple (low-complexity) approach that allows us to detect and identify the faults in the PV systems. This approach will be tested by simulating faulty power plants after the injection of short-circuited module fault in the measurements.

The analyzing, modeling and simulations approaches are developed in the Matlab programming language. In appendice A, there is a brief presentation of this software.

4. Structure of this thesis

The full report delivers analytical and numerical approaches used when analyzing grid-connected PV system performance. It consists in six chapters, with the **first chapter** giving an introduction to the theme of solar energy and the objectives of this study. Afterwards **in chapter 2** an overview on how the solar energy production works explaining the solar cell and PV modules concepts, characteristics, technologies and configurations. Following this, the current state of PV monitoring system is described. Then, a summary of existing methods for PV panel modeling, performance indices & power loss factors is presented. Ending this chapter we have an overview the common faults that occurs in PV systems and summary of faults diagnosis methods recently developed. **Chapter 3** will be given a detailed explanation of the actual grid connected PV systems located in the IUT of Cachan and the data generated by its operation. Finally, the methodology carried out to process and visualize the data will be introduced. **Chapter 4** will give an overview of the three models used to simulate the AC production. We have a detailed explanation of the methodology adopted for the parameter estimation in each model, including the mathematical and numerical background to the work. After that we have results that will be compared to manufacturer’s datasheets or to values found in the literature to validate the models. The simulation framework of the power and the inverter efficiency is covered in this chapter. **Chapter 5** is dedicated to faults diagnosis methods. First, we will present the results and discussions of the comparison between the AC production simulated using the 3 models and the AC measured power. We will analyze the statistical tools obtained over the period of evaluation (6-years) and for different seasons by discussing the effect of ambient temperature and irradiance. We will also explain and define the algorithms and the thresholds used to detect the faults at AC side. Afterwards, we will calculate the previous performance indicators and power loss factors reported in the literature that were the basis of the second faults detection method that focus on the DC side. After will be described the algorithms of failure identification at DC side and the different thresholds related to them. After that we have simulations, results and their discussions. Ending this chapter, there is a study to test the proposed faults diagnosis algorithms. First, we inject short-circuited module fault in the actual monitored data and we simulate the actual PV systems installed at IUT Cachan with faulty state. We implement the previous diagnosis algorithms at both sides and summarize the results. Afterwards, the impacts of one short-circuited module on the output power, voltage and current of a PV systems will be presented. Finally, **chapter 6** presents the final conclusions after analyzing all the work done. Possible variations or upgrades to the proposed methods and approaches are also mentioned for future works.

Chapter 2: Background and Literature Review

In this chapter, a review of literature is presented. The concept of solar cells and modules, including the underlying physics, is introduced to understand the PV panel modeling. PV systems technologies, configurations and monitoring concepts are also introduced. Then, we will describe the types of faults that a typical PV system may suffer from. Then, we will reveal the main methods that currently exist in the literature that can be used to detect and identify these issues.

These concepts are however generic and common knowledge in the field of PV power generation; hence this chapter can be skipped given a sufficient existing background.

1. Theory of the Solar cell and PV module

In order to better understand how a PV module works we have to start by the solar cell.

a. Principles of solar cell operation:

Solar cell can be broadly described as electronic equipment converting incoming photons from sunlight to electric energy. The solar cells of interest in this study are polycrystalline silicon and amorphous silicon technologies that currently have a large market share [5]. Figure 1 shows a simple circuit of a silicon cell with an external load:

Figure1: Schematic of a solar cell connected to a load

When the cell absorbs a photon, if its energy is greater than the band gap of the semiconductor, an electron is able to jump out in the crystal structure creating a hole-electron pair, which normally disappears as the electron recombines with hole. In order to avoid the recombination a barrier is created by doping the silicon, on one side with small amount of a group III element (for ex. Boron) to form p-silicon and on the other side with a small amount of a group V element (for ex. Phosphorus) to form the n-silicon. The presence of the barrier does not allow the recombination, creating an excess of electrons in the n-silicon and a lack of them in the p-silicon. If an external electrical circuit is built the electrons are free to move from the n-silicon to the p-silicon passing by the electrical circuit, thus producing electricity. This is the basic principle behind the solar cell. Depending on the environmental con-

ditions, mainly the irradiation and the temperature, the cell is able to produce a certain voltage and a certain current [5][6][7][8]. This process is just briefly described because this is not the main focus of this thesis is the PV system.

b. From P-N junction to PV cell

An ideal Solar cell can be modeled as a current source connected in parallel with a diode, and the current delivered by an ideal cell is the maximum current (the short circuit current) minus the current that flows through the diode. However, there are inherent losses due to imperfect manufacturing. They are modeled as a series R_s and a parallel resistance R_p . For an ideal cell, R_p would be infinite and would not provide an alternate path for current to flow, while R_s would be zero, resulting in no further voltage drop before the load [5]. These concepts will be throughly explained in the chapter 4. For now let's go back to the basic concepts.

c. From cells to modules and array:

Single solar cells typically generate an output voltage of 0.6V to 0.7V [5][6][7][8]. To produce a larger voltage, a number of cells in series placed into a rigid enclosure to form a module. A typical module may have 36,54,72 or 96 cells in series (Figure 2 left). This thesis considers modules containing 72 and 56 solar cells of the previously specified type (p-Si and a-Si), connected in series.

Multiple modules can be wired in series to increase voltage and in parallel to increase current. Such combinations of modules are referred to as an array (Figure 2 right). In our study, the p-Si PV array contains 8 modules connected in series; and the a-Si PV array contains 16 modules connected also in series.

Figure 2: Configuration of PV module (left) & Configurations from cells to modules and array (right)

2. Characteristic of photovoltaic cell/module

a. The I-V and P-V curves:

The current-voltage relationship characteristic of a solar cell/module is typically characterized with the **I-V curve**. In order to maximize the energy generation of the PV module it is essential that the PV module works at MPP that's why we need a MPPT.

The output power of a PV module is the product of the output current delivered to the electric load and the voltage across the module. The value of the power at **the short-circuit current I_{sc}** (maximum current, occur when the voltage across the device is zero) point is zero; also the power is zero at **the open-circuit voltage V_{oc}** point (the maximum voltage occurs when the current across the device is zero). The maximum output power of the PV module is somewhere in between. This happens at a point called the **maximum power point (MPP)** with the coordinates $V = V_{mpp}$ and $I = I_{mpp}$ [5][6][7][9].

As the output power of the PV module is the product between the current and the voltage, it is then possible to draw also **the power curve** as it can be seen from Figure3. And the maximum power P_{mpp} is calculated as a product of V_{mpp} and I_{mpp} : $P_{mpp} = V_{mpp} I_{mpp}$. **The fill factor** that measures the quality of solar cell is defined as [1][6]: $FF = \frac{V_{mpp} I_{mpp}}{V_{oc} I_{sc}} = \frac{\eta * S_{tot} * G}{V_{oc} I_{sc}}$

Therefore, a higher FF means a higher module performance. The fill factor is 70-80% for crystalline silicon cells. In our study, the polycrystalline PV module has a FF of 74% and 58% for amorphous PV module.

Figure3: I-V and P-V characteristics

b. Scaling I-V curves

When **cells are wired in series**, they are all carry the same current, and their voltage add. The overall module voltage is found by: $V_{module} = N_s(V_d - IR_s)$. Where N_s is number of cells in series; V_d the voltage of the diode; I is the current delivered by the cell and R_s is the serie resistance of the cell.

For **modules in series**, the I-V curves are simply added along the voltage axis. The total voltage is just the sum of the individual module voltages. The figure 4 below on the left shows the I-V curve for 3 modules in series.

For **modules in parallel**, the same voltage is across each module and the total current is the sum of the currents. That is, at any given voltage, the I-V curve of the parallel combination is just the sum of the individual module currents at that voltage. The figure 4 below in the middle shows the I-V curve for 3 modules in parallel.

In high power applications, the array usually consists of a combination of **series and parallel modules** for which the total I-V curve is the sum of the individual module I-V curves. The figure 4 below on the right show 2 parallel strings, each of which containing 3 modules [5][6][7][8].

Figure 4 : Serie Connected modules (left) & Parallel Connected modules(middle) & Series-parallel connected modules(right)

c. Impacts of different parameters on the I-V & P-V curves behavior

The I-V curve shown in Figure 5 is related to standard test conditions (STC: $T_{mod}=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $G=1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$, AM1.5). Sometimes I-V curves may change. Those changes might occur when the following 5 parameters change: shunt/parallel resistances R_p , series resistances R_s , ideality factor of the diode (a), irradiance G , module temperature T_{mod} . The first three parameters are related to the solar cells/PV modules characteristics and the last two are external parameters [5][6][10].

The effect of varying the **ideality factor “a”** can be seen in the figure 5. A higher value of “a” degrades the FF, the power and efficiency, and affects the MPP point in the I-V curve. Hence, the ideal value of “a” is between 1 and 2 [6].

Figure5: Effect of diverging « a » from ideality [10]

Series resistance R_s of the panel has a large impact on the slope of the I-V & P-V curve at $V = V_{oc}$, as seen in the figure 6 on the left. A small change in R_s brings a large change in the FF. However, I_{sc} and V_{oc} are not affected by the change of R_s . Hence, output power is reduced when R_s increases.

It is observed in figure 6 on the right that again I_{sc} and V_{oc} do not vary with **the parallel resistance R_p** . If R_p decreases, the slope of the I-V curve at low voltage (at $I = I_{sc}$) changes (therefore R_p has an impact on the FF). Hence, output power is reduced when R_p decreases.

Figure 6: Effect of diverging R_s (left) & R_p (right) from ideality [10]

As the **module temperature** increases, V_{oc} decreases substantially while I_{sc} increases only slightly \rightarrow PV modules perform better on cold than hot days. – For crystalline silicon cells, V_{oc} drops by about 0.37% for each degree Celsius increase in temperature, and I_{sc} increases by approximately 0.05%/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$, resulting in a decrease in maximum power available by about 0.5 %/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 7 on the left).

As **irradiance** drops, I_{sc} drops in direct proportion. – Decreasing insolation also reduces the V_{oc} , but it does so following a logarithmic relationship that results in relatively modest changes (figure 7 on the right).

Figure 7: Effect of T_{mod} (left) & G (right) on the I-V & P-V curve at $1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$ [10]

Comparing the impacts of R_s , R_p , a , G and T_{mod} on the I-V curve, can be concluded that irradiance has the biggest impact on the I-V curve comparing with the other four model parameters.

3. Different PV module technologies:

There are a wide range of PV technologies as illustrated in Figure 8. They are categorized in many different ways according to the thickness of the layer of the PV material used, to the price and to the efficiency [5].

In this thesis, the simulations and all the work done are based on the following technologies: polycrystalline Silicon (p-Si) with an efficiency of 13.69 % and amorphous Silicon (a-Si) with an efficiency of 6.2%.

Figure 8: Various types of PV cells/modules [11]

In appendice B are some descriptions of these two types of PV technologies.

4. Photovoltaic systems configurations

PV systems are mainly defined based on if the energy generated by the system is stored “**Stand-alone systems**” or it is directly **connected to the grid** [8]. In our study, we will focus more on grid-connected and monitored system, which will be explained and just give an overview of the stand-alone PV system because it’s irrelevant for our present study.

a) Stand-alone PV systems:

They are the most popular system used worldwide. It should provide enough energy to mini-application (pocket calculators, clocks), electrical cars, village electrification, solar pump systems for drinking water and irrigation. Rechargeable batteries are used to store the electricity; and the charge controller prevents overcharging and may prevent against overvoltage of the battery [8].

b) Grid-connected PV systems:

A grid-connected PV power system is electricity generating solar PV power system that is connected to the utility grid. A grid-connected PV system consists of solar panels, one or several inverters, and grid connection equipment. They range from small residential and commercial rooftop systems to large utility-scale solar power stations. Unlike stand-alone power systems, a grid-connected system rarely includes an integrated battery. When conditions are right, the grid connected PV system supplies the excess power, beyond consumption by the connected load, to the utility grid. The grid-connected systems can be monitored automatically. They can display an event number on their screens, like the disconnection of the inverter, which correspond to a different type of faults [8].

The standard configurations of the two systems are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Standard configuration of a stand-alone PV system (left) & Grid-Connected system (right)

5. Grid-connected & monitored PV systems:

The information displayed in this section, along with most of its images, will be based in references [12][13].

a) How it works & its functionalities :

PV monitoring is the act of visualizing and constantly checking the information coming from the system about its state and performance in order to maintain a healthy operation. Nowadays, PV monitoring systems are capable of emitting alerts when the system indicates a problem, which reduce the cost of maintenance and optimize its availability.

The main functionalities incorporated on current PV monitoring software are: **Data acquisition** (from inverters, ground weather sensors/satellite imaging, energy storage, facility load); **Data Aggregation**; **Supervision** (dashboards, alarms, performance metrics, troubleshooting tools); **Production forecasting** (Day/hour-ahead); **Controls** (ramp up/down, Power factor regulation); **Analytics** (trending; Fault prediction); **Reporting** (production, performance, outages/faults) [13].

Not all monitoring systems necessarily have all these functionalities because they still in research phase.

b) Components of grid-connected and monitored PV system

This section aims to give an overview of the different components of a grid connected and monitored PV system, which are the following: **PV modules**; **Junction box**; **by-pass diode**; **Fuses box**; **Wiring**; **Inverter**; **MPPT**; **Temperature sensor** (optional); **Reference solar cell** (optional); **Pyranometer** (optional); **Device for data acquisition “Datalogger”** (optional); **Utility meter** (or bidirectional meters); **Transformer** (or isolation transformer) [12][13].

The inverter converts the DC current generated by the solar cells to a 50 Hz AC current required by the grid. The inverter considered in this study is a **Fronius⁴ inverter** (its characteristics are shown in table 8 in chapter 3).

During the day, the optimum working point on the I-V curve is not fixed in real time, it shifts according to the fluctuations in solar radiation and module temperature. In order to track the most favorable working point, a **MPP tracking (MPPT)** is required to vary the output voltage of the string by maximizing the generated power in any real operating conditions. Actually **MPPT** capabilities are usually included in the inverters used in grid connected PV systems. However, if inverters without MPPT are used, the MPPT algorithm can be separately incorporated into the system between the output of the PV array and the inverter input. The ideal PV system would have an individual MPPT on every PV module and that’s why there are **micro inverters**. The presence of more than one MPPT permits better performance of the entire PV system but the costs would rise too much. Therefore, nowadays is not common to see MPPT on every module of a PV system.

It is common to use **junction boxes**, as can be seen in Fig 10, on every PV module in order to connect them all together, which contains also **bypass diodes**.

Due to the fact that the cells are connected in series, the damage of one of them could affect the performance of the entire panel because the current flowing in the cells is the same and its value will adjust to the worst cell in the panel. Furthermore, if one cell of the panel is shaded, it is going to behave as a resistance, i.e. dissipating the electrical energy as heat. This effect is called **hot spot**. In order to avoid this effect, it is a common practice to introduce in the module **by-pass diodes** that gives to the current an alternative path.

Figure10: Junction Box (left) & Cells connected in series with bypassed diodes (right)

Temperature sensor is used to measure the ambient temperature near the PV plant and the temperature at the module level. **The reference solar cell** enables a high level of measurement precision and is usually used to measure the global irradiance that reaches the PV modules. **The pyranometer** is also used to measure the global horizontal irradiance (GHI). And the pyrheliometer measures the direct normal irradiance (DNI).

On our work in this thesis we use the atmospheric measurements (ambient temperature and irradiance) generated from the **Fronius Sensor Box** that measures the global irradiance in the plane of the array and includes **temperature sensor** (Platinum Resistance thermometer Pt1000⁵) that measures the ambient temperature. Its technical specifications are presented in Appendix B.

Usually, **bi-directional meters** measure the amount of power delivered to the grid and used from the grid, showing the net production or consumption. Since the power meter is positioned between the loads and the grid, it doesn’t only measure the PV production but also to get the return credits from the energy companies because of the energy fees.

Isolation transformers can be optionally placed at the inverter output (AC side) to eliminate the possibility of PV system injecting direct current into the power grid. Some inverters already include transformers of this type incorporated inside while others do not. In most countries this is not required for low voltage connection.

Finally, a **data logger** (electronic device used for storing data in a central database for further analysis) collects the data that comes from **atmospheric sensor box, inverters and bi-directional meters**, on various time intervals, normally every 15 minutes. However, it can range from receiving data every minute to receiving it daily. In our study, **Fronius IG datalogger** (its technical specifications is presented in appendix B) was used for the data acquisition and then the data is sent to the computer. Here, data is gathered and processed by **Fronius software Solar.access** that is an intelligent software for recording, archiving and analysing system data on the PC. It provides a brief overview of the essential data in the system (energy, CO2 emissions savings, heat stroke..). In order **to make all data available online**, network connections are required, which can be made wirelessly or hard-wired (using cables). The data logger used in the acquisition system is normally connected to the Internet through a **router**. Data displaying is usually done through the use of **web portals**, which consist on the viewing platform of the PV system’s data. They can be accessed through a computer, smartphone, tablet, or any other similar device. There are many different web portals available, public or password-secured one, each of them with their own brand logo and their own unique way of displaying information. An application was developed for systems have Fronius inverters that allow their users to register the inverters by simply taking a photo of the inverter’s barcode. In general, the web portals usually display each inverter’s energy production on

⁴ **Fronius** is a residential inverter manufacturer company that offers the complete monitoring service when buying the inverter.

⁵ **Pt1000** is resistance temperature detectors using concept of thermistor. The sensor contains a resistor that changes resistance value as its temperature changes. The platinum strip has a 1000 ohms resistance at 0°C, hence the name PT100.

a daily, monthly, yearly or lifetime basis and the inverter power is normally reported at 15 minutes or hourly intervals. It will also display DC and AC voltage measurements, as well as current measurements. Naturally, it also disconnects from the grid when there is unstable operation. Web portals allow the download of production history reports and they also have the option of reporting data collected from a weather station, if available [13].

Figure 11 contains an overview of a monitoring system and its components and how they interact with each other. Not all monitoring systems necessarily have all the components shown in the figure.

Figure11: Monitoring System Overview

6. State of the art of existing methods for PV panel modeling

As the PV module is considered as the main component of the system, it is important to study the PV module behavior under given operating conditions through modeling.

Electrical, mathematical and empirical have long been implemented and used to simulate the power production of many PV technologies. More details on the different models employed are given below. We're just going to mention here the existing methods for PV module modeling and tackle with more depth on the methodology of our approach later in chapter 4.

a) Electrical Model:

The PV module is characterized by its electrical parameters, and the I-V & P-V curves describing its operation. The performance of PV systems (solar cell/panels), that is, the output current/voltage (*I-V* curve), is usually studied using an **equivalent circuit model**. This equivalent circuit consists of a current source with one or two diodes connected in parallel, and up to two resistors, one connected in parallel and the other one in series, to take into account energy losses in this model. Based on these electronic components, **four basic configurations** (Figure 12) are normally used when studying photovoltaic systems [5][14][15][16][17][18]. However, this list is not exhaustive, there are other models and configurations in the literature that take into account the avalanche in reverse polarization.

The cells and panels have the same form of equations and I-V & P-V curves. The difference is:

$$\begin{cases} I_{panneau} = N_p I_{cell} = I \\ I_{ph,panneau} = N_p I_{ph,cell} = I_{ph} \\ I_{0,panneau} = N_p I_{0,cell} = I_0 \\ V_{panneau} = N_p V_{cell} = V \\ V_{s,panneau} = N_p \frac{KT}{q} = V_s \\ R_{s,panneau} = \frac{N_p}{N_p} R_{s,cell} = R_s \\ R_{p,panneau} = \frac{N_p}{N_p} R_{p,cell} = R_p \\ a_{panneau} = a_{cell} = a \end{cases}$$

Figure12: Four different equivalent circuit models: (a) 1-diode; (b) 1-diode/1-resistor; (c) 1-diode/2 resistors; (d) 2-diodes/2 resistors;

Hence, the solar module output current I is given by the following equations for each configuration (by applying the Kirchhoff's rule) [5][6][14][15][16][17][19][20][21][22][23]:

Table1: The main equation of each configuration of equivalent circuit models

a) The Single-Diode-Model "SDM" (The ideal/ 1-diode Model): The most simplified form of an ideal PV cell. But this model doesn't provide accurate I-V and P-V curve characteristics.	$I = I_{ph} - I_d = I_{ph} - I_{01} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V}{a_1 V_t}\right) - 1 \right]$
b) The SDM with 4 parameters (The 1-diode/1-resistor model): It takes into account the internal losses caused by the interconnections of cells to form arrays.	$I = I_{ph} - I_d = I_{ph} - I_{01} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{a_1 V_t}\right) - 1 \right]$
c) The SDM with 5 parameters (The 1-diode/2-resistors model) consists of a conventional electrical model	$I = I_{ph} - I_d - I_{sh} = I_{ph} - I_{01} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{a_1 V_t}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V + IR_s}{R_p}$
d) The 2-diodes/2-resistors model: yields more accurate results than SDM. It takes into account the effect of recombination by introducing another diode in parallel.	$I = I_{ph} - I_d - I_{sh} = I_{ph} - I_{01} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{a_1 V_t}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{02} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{a_2 V_t}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V + IR_s}{R_p}$

The electrical model (depending on each configuration) accurately simulates current-voltage (I-V) curves, power-voltage (P-V) curves, including maximum power point values, short-circuit current and open-circuit voltage across a range of irradiation levels and module temperatures.

Obviously, some **parameters of these equations** need to be estimated to adapt the corresponding model to the real performance of the panel behavior. The tables 2 and 3 below summarizes the parameters of each configuration and parameters meaning:

Table2: Model parameters of different configurations

Configuraton	Number of parameters	Parameters
(a)	3	I_{ph}, I_{01}, a_1
(b)	4	I_{ph}, I_{01}, a_1, R_s
(c)	5	$I_{ph}, I_{01}, a_1, R_s, R_p$
(d)	7	$I_{ph}, I_{01}, a_1, I_{02}, a_2, R_s, R_p$

Table3: Model Parameters Meanings

Parameters	Meanings
$I_{ph} (A)$	The photocurrent is generated by solar irradiation and flows to the output
$I_{01} (A)$	The reverse saturation current of the first diode
$I_{02} (A)$	The reverse saturation current of the second diode
$I_{03} (A)$	The reverse saturation current of the third diode
a_1	The first diode ideality factor, takes into account the imperfect junction (due the carrier recombination as the charge carrier cross the depletion zone). It typically varies from 1 to 2 (though can in some cases be higher) depending on the fabrication process and semiconductor material and is set equal 1 for the case of an "ideal diode" (thus the n is omitted) [6].
a_2	The second diode ideality factor
a_3	The third diode ideality factor
$R_s (\Omega)$	Series resistance is introduced as to consider the voltage drops and internal losses in due to flow of current. As an approximation [22]: $R_s < \frac{0.1V_{oc}}{I_{sc}}$
$R_p (\Omega)$	Parallel resistance takes into account the leakage current (in the P-N junction) to the ground when diode is in reverse biased. As an approximation [22]: $R_p > \frac{10V_{oc}}{I_{sc}}$
$V_{th} = N_s k T_{mod} / q$	The thermal voltage, where $k=1.38065 \cdot 10^{-23} J/K$ is the Boltzmann constant, T_{mod} the temperature expressed in kelvin, and $q=1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C$ is the electron charge, and N_s is the number of series-connected cells in the photovoltaic system to be analyzed. [22]

The equations of these parameters (I_{ph}, I_0, a, R_s, R_p), which describe the I-V characteristics of the module at different operating point (G, T_{mod}) are summarized in the table 4 below:

Table4: Mathematical equations for plotting I-V and P-V Curves in operating conditions [22][23]

The photo-current I_{ph}: depends on T_{mod} and G [21]	$I_{ph}(G, T_{mod}) = [I_{ph,STC} + K_I(T_{mod} - T_{STC})] \frac{G}{G_{STC}}$
Dart saturation current I_0: is related to the bandgap of semiconductor and temperature [20] [21].	$I_0(G, T_{mod}) = I_{0,STC} \left(\frac{T_{mod}}{T_{STC}}\right)^3 \exp\left[\frac{qE_g}{ak} \left(\frac{1}{T_{STC}} - \frac{1}{T_{mod}}\right)\right]$ Where: $E_g = E_{g,STC} [1 - 0.002677 * (T_{mod} - T_{STC})]$ [24] $E_{g,STC} = 1.12eV$ for polycrystalline [25]; $E_{g,STC} = 1.75eV$ for amorphous[25]

The series resistance R_s; The shunt resistance R_p and the ideality factor “a” are assumed constants [21]. No matter the operating condition, the value of a, R_s, R_p will not change.	$R_p = R_{p,STC}$ $R_s = R_{s,STC}$ $a = a_{STC}$

But for evaluating these parameters at different operating point, manufacturer given output characteristics ($I_{ph,STC}, I_{0,STC}, a_{STC}, R_{s,STC}, R_{p,STC}$) are required. Manufacturers don't provide these unknown parameters at STC. Thus, these processes can be cumbersome and evaluating these constants becomes very difficult. Since these constants affect the I-V curve and their correct estimation improves the model accuracy, they must be evaluated accurately without assumptions.

Literature Review of Parameter estimation approach:

The SDM with 5 parameters is the conventional electrical Model. Several studies have been devoted and many authors discuss various ways to evaluate the unknown parameters ($I_{ph,STC}, I_{0,STC}, a_{STC}, R_{s,STC}, R_{p,STC}$) and I-V curves modelization. One can distinguish the analytical methods, which make it possible to calculate independently each parameter according to **given limiting conditions** around **key operational points included in manufacturers' datasheets**: the short circuit point ($I = I_{SC}, V = 0$), the open circuit point ($I = 0, V = V_{OC}$) and the maximum power point ($I = I_{mpp}, V = V_{mpp}$). Other piece of information is usually determined from the slope of the I-V curve (Figure 13): at the open circuit voltage $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=V_{oc}} = -\frac{1}{R_s}$ and at the short circuit current $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{I=I_{sc}} = -\frac{1}{R_p}$ [16][17]. The slope in SC and OC, if it's not directly provided, it can be approximated by plotting the points, provided by the manufacturer's datasheet and determining the slope between the SC and the MPP, or the OC and the MPP.

Figure13: The relationship between the I-V curve and R_s & R_p

Another piece of information can be derived using the fact that on the P-V characteristics of a PV system at the MPP, the derivative of power with respect to voltage is zero: $\left(\frac{dP}{dV}\right)_{V_{mp}, I_{mp}} = I + V \frac{dI}{dV} = 0$

Some authors have further simplified the **SDM with 5 parameters** by removing the shunt resistance R_p as the value of this resistance is generally high to obtain a model of moderate complexity referred to as the **four parameters model**. The four parameters model assumes that the slope of the I-V curve is flat at the short-circuit condition: $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=0} = 0$. However, this assumption is not generally valid for amorphous PV systems. The short circuit I-V slope is finite and negative, so the four parameters model cannot reproduce the I-V characteristics of amorphous silicon, for example [26].

Sometimes, the series resistance R_s is also neglected, as its value is very low thus reducing the accuracy of the proposed model [16]. Iterative calculations have been carried out recently using **artificial intelligence (AI) techniques** such as **fuzzy logic (FL)** and **artificial neural network (ANN)**. Some authors estimate these constants by curve fitting and optimization (the concept of the **minimum sum of squares** based on **Lambert W-function** or **Newton's Raphson method**). Another **genetic algorithms** such as **particle swarm optimization (PSO)** have also been proposed.

Summary & Configuration chosen in our study:

Various configurations for modeling PV are suggested, however the SDM and two-diode models seem as the most common models used for modeling solar module. For simplicity, the single-diode model of Fig 12 (b)-(c) is studied in this work. This model offers a good compromise between simplicity and accuracy, and has been used by numerous authors [10]. Due to the presence of the diode, the equivalent circuit no longer remains linear and hence, it is difficult to solve the equations of current and voltage for the PV because it is difficult to find out the analytical solution of the unknown parameters in this SDM. One has to rely on numerical techniques to compute the current (or voltage) iteratively.

The objective is once we obtain the unknown parameters of SDM ($I_{ph,STC}, I_{0,STC}, a_{STC}, R_{s,STC}, R_{p,STC}$), depending on which model (4 or 5 parameters), the parameters (I_{ph}, I_0, a, R_s, R_p) can be calculated, hence the current delivered by the panel is calculated and

the I-V curve of each operating point is computed and hence **the maximum power output** is found:

$$P_{mpp,sim} = \max (V_{mpp,sim} I_{mpp,sim})$$

To simulate the AC production, we have to simulate the inverter efficiency: $P_{ac,sim} = P_{mpp,sim} * \eta_{inv,sim}$

b) Evans Model:

An alternative approach to modelize the power output is the Evans Model based on datasheet parameters, solar irradiance and modules temperature. However, this approach doesn't provide I-V and P-V curves.

The direct electric power $P_{mpp,sim}$ generated by a PV module is given by the product of the total active area of the module $N_{mod,s} S_u$, the solar irradiance G , conversion efficiency of the module η . In our study, we only have modules connected in series $N_{mod,s}$. The model is expressed by [27]: $P_{mpp,sim} = \eta * G * N_{mod,s} * S_u$

The model is based on a parametric approach to model the PV efficiency [28]:

$$\eta = \eta_{fit} \left[1 + K_{p,fit}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \gamma_{fit} \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right) \right]$$

$\eta_{fit}, K_{p,fit}, \gamma_{fit}$ obtained by filtering the data and fitting the model equation with measurement data. We can also use the parameters provided by the manufacturer or found in the literature. As the efficiency measured is provided at the AC side, hence the efficiency of the module fitted takes into account the inverter efficiency, $\eta_{fit} = \eta_{PV,sim} \eta_{inv,sim}$ and the inverter efficiency $\eta_{inv,sim}$ is assumed constant.

The AC production simulated is then: $P_{ac,sim} = \eta_{fit} \left[1 + K_{p,fit}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \gamma_{fit} \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right) \right] * G * N_{mod,s} * S_u$

The module temperature is calculated using NOCT Model, which is described in chapter 3 (section 2).

c) Empirical Model (PVUSA):

An alternative approach to predict the power of a photovoltaic PV system based exclusively on atmospheric measurements: G, T_{amb} . However, this approach, like Evans Model, doesn't provide I-V and P-V curves.

The direct electric power $P_{mpp,sim}$ generated by a PV module is given by [29]: $P_{mpp,sim} = G (a + bG + cT_{amb} + d.WS)$

In our study, we neglect the wind speed (WS=0) because it is not available in the outdoor measurements.

a, b, c are coefficients calculated, so that the model result is as close as possible to the measured data.

With the same assumption as we used with Evans Model, these parameters are found by filtering the data and fitting the model equation with measurement data. As the power measured is provided at the AC side, hence the power of the module takes into account the inverter efficiency $\eta_{inv,sim}$ which is assumed constant.

The AC production simulated is then: $P_{ac,sim} = G (a_{fit} + b_{fit}G + c_{fit}T_{amb})$

It's important to notice that PVUSA model is the combination of NOCT Model and Evans model without the last term characterizing low irradiance $\gamma \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right)$.

7. Performance & power loss indicators of grid connected PV systems

These indicators will be used in the last chapter when we will implement the fault detection method at the DC side, but in order to better understand this review, here is a quick overview of the energy yields and power loss factors in a PV system.

a) Performance indices:

International Energy Agency (IEA) Photovoltaic Power System Program established performance indices that evaluate the overall performance of the grid-tied PV system and, they can also be used to compare the performance of any system with similar installations irrespective of the location and installed capacity.

These performance parameters are the energy output; energy yields (reference yield (Y_r), array yield (Y_a), final yield (Y_f)), the performance ratio (PR), and the capacity factor (CF) [30][31][32].

Depending on the available data and desire period of time, these performance metrics can be determined on instantaneous, hourly, daily, monthly and annually bases. The interval of measure should be converted in hour (h) and should be constant otherwise we should use the integral $\int P * dt$ instead of $\sum P * t$ in the equations presented in tables 5 and 6.

A detailed explanation of each one of the parameters will be explained in detail in the table 5 below. But let's first take a look to the figure 14. It illustrates the energy flow in a grid-connected photovoltaic system describing the main energy conversion steps taking place within the system.

Figure14: Energy flow & Loss mechanisms in a grid-connected photovoltaic system

Table5: Summary of the performance parameters

Parameter	Description	Mathematical expression	Unit
The energy output	The amount of alternating current (AC) power P produced by the system over a given period of time.	$E = \sum_{t=1}^{period} P * t$	(Wh/period)
The reference yield	The equivalent amount of hours where $G_{STC}=1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.	$Y_r = \frac{\sum_{period} G * t}{G_{STC}}$	(h/period)
The corrected reference yield [32]	It reflects the decrease of the production due to the modules' PV modules work with a T_{mod} above 25°C .	$Y_{CR} = Y_r [1 - K_{p,STC} (T_{mod} - T_{STC})]$	(h/period)
The array yield	The number of hours where the installed PV system produces its rated output DC power	$Y_a = \frac{\sum_{period} P_{dc} * t}{P_{mpp,STC} * N_{mod}}$	(h/period)
The final/system yield	It is defined as the AC energy output of the system, at given period, divided by the rated or nominal power of the installed PV array at STC.	$Y_f = \frac{\sum_{period} P_{ac} * t}{P_{mpp,STC} * N_{mod}}$	(h/period)
The performance ratio	It quantifies the total losses when converting from DC to AC due to inverter efficiency, wiring mismatch; module temperature; incomplete use of irradiance by reflection from the module front surface; soiling or snow; system down-time; and component failures.	-The DC PR: $PR_{dc} = \frac{Y_a}{Y_r} * 100$ -The AC PR : $PR_{ac} = \frac{Y_f}{Y_r} * 100$	(%)
The Capacity factor/ Load factor	The ratio of AC energy produced by the PV system over a given period of time (usually one year) to the energy output that would have been generated if the system were operated at full capacity for the entire period (operated with its total installed "nominal" power 24 h a day over a year).	$CF = \frac{\sum_{period} P_{ac} * t}{(P_{mpp,STC} * N_{mod}) * period}$	(%)
The complement of the load factor [31]	The ratio of the energy that is not produced over a given period of time and the energy it would have produced if it had operated at its nominal power during the same period.	$\lambda = \frac{\lambda_{annual} * 100}{8760}$ $\lambda_{annual} = \sum_{year} (1 - t_{available}) = 1 - (CF * 8760)$	(%)

b) Power loss factors:

Overall losses in PV systems happen in both DC and AC sides and are influenced by a number of factors (Figure 14). The main loss factors are the following [30][31][32].:

Table6: Summary of the Power Loss Factors

Power loss factor	Description	Mathematical Expression	Unit
Capture Losses	This kind of losses occur mainly at the DC side of the PV system and they are attributed to operating temperature, PV efficiency temperature dependency, dependency on solar irradiance level, shading and losses when sunlight is at a high angle of incidence (AOI). The capture losses can be divided into two kinds of losses [32]: Thermal losses are due to the decrease in DC output power when the PV modules are working at temperatures higher than reference temperature (25°C). Miscellaneous capture losses are mainly due to shading, wiring, ohmic losses, low irradiance losses, angle of incidence losses, losses caused by	-Thermal losses : $L_{ct} = Y_a(G, 25^\circ\text{C}) - Y_a(G, T_{mod})$ or : $L_{ct} = Y_r - Y_{CR}$ - Miscellaneous capture losses $L_{cm} = Y_r(G, T_{mod}) - Y_a(G, 25^\circ\text{C})$ -Capture losses : $L_c = L_{ct} + L_{cm} = Y_r(G, T_{mod}) - Y_a(G, T_{mod})$ $Y(G, T_{mod})$ are the energy yields at real working irradiance and module temperature.	(Wh/Wp_period)

	faulty operation at the DC side (faulty strings, faulty modules, partial shadowing, short circuit of modules), MPP tracker failure, dirt accumulation.		
System Losses	Losses due to the conversion from DC power output of PV to AC power output of the inverter	$L_s = Y_a - Y_f$	(Wh/Wp_period)

8. Theory of faults diagnosis in PV systems

Monitoring systems are essential to maintain optimal performance of photovoltaic (PV) systems. A critical aspect in such monitoring systems is the fault diagnosis technique being used.

This section gives an overview of possible types of faults and describes some faults diagnosis methods that have been established by some studies.

a. Introduction to faults diagnosis

The fault diagnosis method must perform the three main tasks [8][25][33]:

- **Detection**, which consists in making a binary decision: the system works correctly or a failure has occurred.
- **Location/isolation**, which consists in locating the failed component.
- **Identification**, of the causes affecting the real-time energy production and/or smooth functioning of PV systems.

b. Overview of typical Issues in PV systems

When PV system is under operation, it is subject to several inherent power losses that can appear on the DC and AC outputs of a PV system [7][12][33][34][35]. Any factor, which reduces the output, is considered as “fault”. It may be **temporary** (irradiance is lowered by the angle of incidence AOI, shadows during the early hours of the day and sometimes late in the afternoon, bird droppings, and dust or snow accumulation on the surface of the PV panel) or **permanent** (electrical disconnection of the system from the grid, hot spot, wiring losses, string/MPPT failures and ageing). A permanent fault would remain for prolonged time whereas a temporary fault can be cleared within a specific time period. The classification of the most common types of faults in PV system is enumerated in appendice B.

It’s important to keep in mind that some faults are not picked up by the inverters because they are not system anomalies, meaning they don’t occur because a component is malfunctioning but rather because of external factors. Hence, they are **not automatically detectable faults**.

The automatical detectable faults occur at **inverter level**: they stop when there is a **problem in the AC cabling**, which causes the inverter to not be able to connect to the grid until the quality of such connections is ensured. To solve this problem, the entire AC cabling must be checked to make sure it is correctly connected and the cables are intact, along with the fuses. The AC voltages at the connection point must be measured as well.

The unstable operation of the inverter happens when the power supply at the DC input is not high enough for the inverter to operate properly. The inverter has a minimum amount of input power needed to operate, and if that minimum is not met, the inverter cannot connect to the grid until that value of input power is reached. As soon as these values go back to normal, the inverter switches itself back on. The same happened when the current and power values reached zero and the voltage has its maximum value, which corresponds to a situation of open circuit (V_{oc}). As a consequence of this fault, both the delivered active power and the AC voltage hit the value of zero while the fault persists.

The diagnosis appears in the inverter when one of **its fans is blocked** and must be cleaned. It is responsible for a constant loss in power that eventually amounts to a big value and needs to be addressed if it persists for a very long time. Generally, Inverters register this fault on every day with good or mostly good weather. The only days in which the inverter doesn’t register this fault are cloudy ones. The system’s inverter can also **deliver power that is inferior to the nominal power** for duration equal or higher than 10 minutes due to excessive temperatures.

Different studies discuss also the following failures in solar modules [8][25][36]:

Yellowing & browning, delamination, bubbles in the solar module, Cracks in cell, Defects in anti-reflective coating; Ground faults which is defined as a conductor accidentally having contact with the system ground; **Line-line faults** that occur when two different potentials conduct by accident; **Open-circuit faults** occur when a conductor is accidentally removed from a closed circuit (figure 15). The literature concludes that ground and line-line faults typically exhibit a significant drop in output voltage, and also states that open-circuit faults and degradation causes significant decrease current. Hence, reducing power output.

Figure15: Typical issues in PV systems

Faults can occur in a PV array and generate different effects on the performance and lifetime of PV system. Therefore, it is necessary to identify what kind of failures can be found in the real system. Despite main power reduction causes are known, it is very hard to quantify separately the amount of power reduction.

c) Existing Faults diagnosis Methods & Approaches chosen in our study:

Various fault detection methods were reported in literature. Among all the fault detection techniques reported, some paid significant attention only on **faults on DC side** of the PV system while the rest focused on **AC side faults**. Overall, faults can be detected visually or with the help of more advanced methods [8][12][25][33][34][35][36]. In appendix B are presented some faults diagnosis Method reported in literature.

Most fault detection algorithms reported in the literature follow the idea of **comparing monitored data from the PV system with model prediction (CMM) results** to identify faults when significant differences are observed between the two sets of data. This is the approach we have used in this work. The idea is to compare the measured output power with the modeled one using statistical indicators to calculate and classify significant deviations. It is based on the fact that if measurements deviates from the model it's indicates an issue.

The second fault detection method used in this study is based on **Power loss analysis (PLA)**. This technique is based on the analysis of power losses in the PV array and Power losses are calculated by comparing the monitored data with simulated power losses at the DC side.

These techniques establish theoretical thresholds and trigger an alarm when some parameters (production, power losses, current, voltage..) are outside normal thresholds. However, if it does exceed the threshold then the system is considered to be faulty. In some approaches, the expected value of PV outputs was predicted with parametric models and weather variables along with adjustable parameter. In this work, we used 3 models to predict power output: the single-diode-model with 5 parameters; Evans Model and Empirical Model. All parameters are retrieved from the manufacturers datasheet and through parameter extraction using particular conditions and historical data measurements of one year 2011.

In the case of given knowledge surrounding faults it is possible to inject faults in the measurements to test the fault diagnosis method developed. In our study, we aim to study the faults on DC side (faulty string and short-circuited modules). But, as we have only 1 string for each technology and the modules are connected in series, we focused only on short-circuited modules.

Chapter3: Data description, processing and Analysis

This section describes the PV system analyzed in this work, the monitoring devices of the modules, and the monitoring data received from the setup.

1. System and Data description:

The present work analyzes the performance of two grid-connected and monitored PV systems that are placed into the same location, on the roof of the building IUT in the area of Cachan in France. The PV installation is shown in figure 16.

Figure16: Outdoor PV modules installation (Si polycrystalline & Si amorphous)

The PV modules investigated, are based on two silicon modules technologies : The **SCHOTT polycrystalline modules (p-Si)** which contains 72 solar cells connected in series, with a maximum power of 180W, and **the SCHOTT amorphous module (a-Si)** based on 56 solar cells connected in series, which generate a maximum power of 90W. In total, the PV plants is formed by 16 amorphous panels and 8 polycrystallines modules connected in series. The PV plant is equipped with two **Fronius IG 15 in-**

verters, one for each technology, operating simultaneously. The inverters automatically stop delivering active power to the grid when there is unstable operation.

The specifications under standard test conditions (STC) of the PV modules of each technology are given in table 7, and the specification of the inverter are presented in table 8.

Table 7 : Technical specifications of PV modules given by the manufacturer

	Polycrystallines (p-Si)	Amorphous (a-Si)
Data under STC (1000W/m², AM 1.5, Tcell=25°C)		
Nominal power $P_{mpp,STC}$ (Wp)	180	90
Voltage at MPP $V_{mpp,STC}$ (V)	36.3	17.3
Current at MPP $I_{mpp,STC}$ (A)	4.95	5.21
Open-Circuit voltage $V_{oc,STC}$ (V)	44.6	23.4
Short-circuit current $I_{sc,STC}$ (A)	5.39	6.6
Module Efficiency η_{PV} (%)	13.69	6.22
Data under NOCT (800 W/m², AM1.5, V=1m/s, Tamb=20°C)		
Nominal power (Wp)	144	79
Voltage at MPP (V)	36.5	17.3
Current at MPP (A)	3.95	
Open-Circuit voltage $V_{oc,STC}$ (V)	44.8	23.5
Short-circuit current $I_{sc,STC}$ (A)	4.3	5.43
Temperature of cells T_{NOCT} (°C)	47.1	49
Coefficient of T		
Power $K_p,STC(P_{nom})$ (%/°C)	-0.47	-0.2
Open-Circuit voltage $K_v(V_{oc})$ (%/°C)	-0.38	-0.33
Short-circuit current $K_i(I_{sc})$ (%/°C)	0.1	0.08
Technical specifications		
Manufacturer	Schott Solar Poly	Schott Solar ASI
Number of panels in serie $N_{mod.s}$	8	16
Total Surface S_{tot} (m2)	10.5	22.4
Number of Solar Cells connected in serie per module N_s	72	56
Unit Area S_u (m2)	1.620*0.81	1.108*1.308

Table 8 : Characteristics of Fronius Inverter IG15

Maximum efficiency $\eta_{inv,STC}$ (%)	94.2
Power Input (Wp) /Power Output (W)	1200-1300/ 1300

Fronius IG Sensors Box is setup to measure the global irradiance in the plane of the array G (W/m²) and include Resistance thermometer Pt1000⁶) to measure the ambient temperature T_{amb} (°C) for amorphous modules.

The data acquisition is carried out using the **Fronius datalogger box** (one for each technology) that receives and stores electrical data from the inverters and meteorological data from Fronius IG sensor box every 15 min and then the data is sent to the computer running Microsoft windows with an intelligent software for recording, archiving and analyzing system data on the computer. To monitor the data, we can make all data available online, and each data logger is connected to the Internet through **a router**, to be able to access through a computer to the web portals displaying the information of the PV system. Web portals allow the download of data collected from weather sensors and from inverters. For our case, we didn't have access to the web portals; we directly have Excel files containing measurements for each technology over the period of evaluation (from 2011 to 2016) from the team working in the PV installation.

The block diagram of this PV installation is shown in figure 17. And a detailed connection scheme of our monitoring system is shown in appendice C.

⁶ **Pt1000** is resistance temperature detectors using concept of thermistor. The sensor contains a resistor that changes resistance value as its temperature changes. The platinum strip has a 1000 ohms resistance at 0°C, hence the name PT100.

Figure 17 : Schematic representation of the PV arrays and data acquisition systems of poly-Si (left) & Amorphous-Si (right)

The measurements are taken at regular intervals (every 15 minutes from sunrise to sunset). At each measurement the software records the environmental and electrical parameters and save the data into different Excel text files. The **electrical measured** quantities include the AC power and voltages at both sides (DC and AC). And the **atmospheric measurements** include global irradiance in the plane of the array and ambient temperature.

For this study, we have data files of electrical and atmospheric measurements during the period of 6 years, taken from from April 6th, 2011 to October 6th, 2016. The content of these files is listed in table 9.

Table 9: The data measured by the PV installation

Recorded Data	Parameter	Symbol	Unit
	Date and Time		dd-mmm-yyyy HH:MM
Solar Irradiance		G	W/m ²
Ambient temperature		T_{amb}	°C
PV array output voltage		$V_{dc, meas}$	V
Grid AC voltage		$V_{ac, meas}$	V
Power to utility grid		$P_{ac, meas}$	W

The table 10 below provides information of the disponible measurements and the period when the measurements were available.

Table10: Summary of the operating period before data processing & Data control quality

	Year	Disponible measurements	Unavailable measurements	Period of disponible measurements
Amorphous	2011	$T_{amb}, G, V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}	6Apr-31 Dec (9months)
	2012	$T_{amb}, G, V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}	1 Jan-14 Dec (11months)
	2013	$T_{amb}, G, V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}	5 Sep-31Dec (4months)
	2014	$T_{amb}, G, V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}	1 Jan-10 Mar (2months)
	2015	$T_{amb}, G, V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}	22 Oct-31 Dec (2months)
	2016	$T_{amb}, G, V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}	1 Jan-6 Oct (9.5 months)
Polycrystallines	2011	$V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}, T_{amb}, G	6 Apr-31 Dec (9months)
	2012	$V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}, T_{amb}, G	1 Jan-21 Dec (12 months)
	2013	$V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}, T_{amb}, G	25 Jan-31 Dec (11 months)
	2014	$V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}, T_{amb}, G	1Jan-5 Sep (8months)
	2015	$V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}, T_{amb}, G	28 May-31 Dec (7months)
	2016	$V_{dc, meas}, V_{ac, meas}, P_{ac, meas}$	T_{mod}, T_{amb}, G	1 Jan-6Oct (9months)

This table shows the operating period of each inverter (for each PV module technology). It looks like that the inverter connected to the polycrystalline PV modules had been operating for almost all the year, while the inverter connected to the amorphous had only been operating almost all the year only in 2011, 2012 and 2016. But in 2013, 2014 and 2015 there is no enough data, the inverter has only been operating for around 2 or 4 months.

It is important to note that the atmospheric measurements are disponible only for amorphous. Since solar irradiance and ambient temperature do not depend on technology, the atmospheric data of polycrystalline was recovered from amorphous. The methodology of data recovery will be explained in the next section (Data Control Quality). After Data Quality Control and the recovery of atmospheric data of polycrystallines, we have the same period of measurements for both technologies corresponding to the measurements of amorphous.

One can easily recognize that the periods when the measurements were not taken are different from one year to another. The periods when the measurements were not available are less than one month. Moreover, after sunset the system is completely shutdown.

It is also important to note that during the first and last periods of the day, when the value of solar irradiance is low the inverters cannot connect to the grid until the input power reach a certain value. We won't tell too much on this event right now since it will be explained in one of the next sections (Data filtering).

2. Calculated parameter: Model of module temperature

As can be seen in table 10 above, the unavailable measurements include the module temperature.

Naturally, to measure the module temperature T_{mod} , we have similar device for measuring the ambient temperature “Fronius Sensor Box” using Pt 1000 or generally a device that is attached to the backside of the module. However, in this study, we don't have access to the measurement of the module temperature.

The following expression is used to calculate the temperature of the module by the NOCT model, using irradiance and ambient temperature measurements [22][37][38]: $T_{mod} = T_{amb} + \frac{G}{800} (T_{NOCT} - 20)$

The Nominal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT) is defined as the temperature reached by the module under the following conditions: $G = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$, $T_{amb} = 20^\circ\text{C}$, wind speed = 1 m/s.

3. Description of Data Processing and Analysis

As we knew that PV module's data is very important for modeling and it requires the accuracy to obtain the good results. Prior to model development, the data should be analyzed and processed.

This section will give an overview on how the data generated by our PV installation was processed. However, for the rest of the report, we will omit most of the programming technicalities and skip straight to the important information about the PV systems.

Figure 18 shows a schematic diagram where the steps that are carried out in the developed approach for processing and visualizing the data measurements.

Figure 18: Diagram of Monitored Data Processing

Data Collection: Historical data were collected from the PV systems (16 polycrystallines modules and 9 amorphous modules) mounted, with their monitoring system, on the roof of IUT Cachan, France. Measurements recorded every 15 min, covering the period of April 2011-October 2016, of the solar irradiance, ambient temperature, DC voltage, AC voltage and AC power output. This data was extracted from an Excel file (.xls) and processed using a programming language in Matlab to perform the analysis presented in this thesis. We have 6 excel files for each technology, which means 12 excel files in total.

Data importation: the information provided to us on an Excel file had to be imported to matfile capable of performing the analysis we wanted and draw conclusions about the systems. In order to import this information to MATLAB environment, we had to create and run a script that told the program how exactly it was supposed to handle the Excel file.

Data Control Quality: it consists on checking and identifying the missing data. At this point we must make a decision on how to handle the atmospheric data of polycrystalline that failed the data quality: “Replacing the failed data with an average value”. “Replacing the failed data with historic data from a similar conditions”. “Removing the failed data from the dataset”. We finally decided to recover the missing data of polycrystalline (atmospheric measurements) from amorphous, since the ambient temperature and solar irradiance are independent from the technology. We also validate the data recovery by comparing the plots of atmospheric data as a function of time of a-Si with those of p-Si over the 6 years of evaluation. The graphs obtained confirm that the data recovery has been done successfully (Appendice C).

Data Averaging: The original 15-min measurements were averaged over 1h by taking the average of neighbouring points. Only hourly averages measurements were used to develop the models of the AC power production and faults diagnosis methods because it reduces the measurements variability and ultimately simplify the approach of faults diagnosis.

Data Visualization : Data processing allows a large volume of data set to be simultaneously represented in a readable way, enabling us to quickly detect patterns that would require any type of quality control ; Thus data visualization throughout the monitoring period, or displaying only daily/weekly/monthly data, gives us information about the behavior of panels and inverters, as well as possible deviations from normal operation or anomalous situations, can be obtained at a glance. The instants of time at which such events take place can be quickly detected. Therefore, Data processing and quality control developed in this study, ease the comprehension and interpretation of large amounts of data, even if it comprises several years.

Date filtering: As said before when explaining the faults that occur at inverter level, during the first and last periods of the day, the inverter didn't receive enough input power. In these moments, the DC voltage values appear to be very high before rapidly decreasing to normal values this corresponds to an open circuit situation since the inverter is not connected to the grid before dawn. This situation occurs only on a few hours at dawn or dusk when the sun is low. Thus, it should be no major cause for concern, as it typically goes away when the irradiation levels rise. It could be a cause for concern if, however, the problem would persist during the rest of the day, which doesn't happen in this case.

Hence, the first step of the faults diagnosis was the elimination of observations corresponding to very low sunlight levels (less than $200\text{W}/\text{m}^2$) for which the measurement accuracy is significantly reduced; and to avoid the weird behavior of the inverter for very low irradiation ($P_{ac} < 100\text{W}$).

An example (Figure 19) of this unstable operation is presented in the figure below by plotting the AC measured power as a function of solar irradiance using the 15-min measurements over the first year of evaluation 2011:

As can be seen in figure 19, under $100\text{W}/\text{m}^2$, the measured AC power and solar irradiance don't follow a linear relationship for both technologies. Hence, to avoid the weird behavior of the inverter at low sun, we filter all irradiance below $200\text{W}/\text{m}^2$ in each year.

For $G > 200\text{W}/\text{m}^2$, one can easily see that there is no strong linear relationship of the measured AC power with irradiance for polycrystalline (Figure 19 left), compared to amorphous modules (figure 19 right). This problem will be explained in the next paragraph (Data Control Quality).

Figure 19: The unstable operation of the inverters for very low irradiance ($G < 200\text{W}/\text{m}^2$) for both technologies : Poly2011 (left) & Amorphous 2011(Right)

Data control quality failures: After the process of data recovery, the plots of atmospheric data as a function of time for the two technologies in each year were similar which confirm that the data recovery has been done successfully (Appendice C). However lags can be present in the dataset recovered, due to improper synchronization between sampling times of different measurements (electrical and atmospheric).

Under normal conditions, the solar irradiance and power production measurements follow a strong linear relationship. In order to detect observations not representative of a normal PV system operation that can be caused by the data recovery of polycrystallines, the plot of the AC power as a function of the irradiance was examined: Observations close to the irradiance-power linear relationship line are considered as normal operation measurements (figure 19 right for amorphous and figure 21 right for poly-Si), while observations far from this line are considered as problem in data synchronization (figure 20) [39].

The normal and abnormal observations were identified through visual inspection by analyzing the abnormal production and the significant difference between the width of curves in the graphs below (figure 20 and 21) when the system produces significantly less or more power than it should at the given irradiance level.

Figure20: 15-min (red curve) & hourly (blue curve) measurements of polycrystalline 2016 after atmospheric data recovery

Figure21: 15-min (red curve) & hourly (blue curve) measurements of polycrystalline 2011 after atmospheric data recovery

For the 15-min measurements (the red curve in Figure 20), the abnormal points located above the irradiance-power straight line occur mostly at irradiance under $700\text{W}/\text{m}^2$. Most of them correspond to abnormally high power production at relatively low sunlight levels. These values are evidently erroneous; they may be caused by lagging between the irradiance and ambient temperature taken from amorphous and power measurements taken from the inverter connected to polycrystallines modules.

The abnormal points located below the line occur at almost all irradiance levels, and most of them are still present when the 15-min measurements are hourly averaged (the blue curve in figure 20), especially at irradiance under $700\text{W}/\text{m}^2$. It means that the production is abnormally low despite relatively high sunlight levels.

This lagging does last for a long period from 2012 to 2016, and its effect is quite reduced when averaging 4 consecutive 15-min measurements into one hourly value (the blue curve in Figure 20). In fact, if the lag is below 1h it can be smoothed when averaging the data, otherwise there is a problem.

As can be seen in figure 21, we don't see this effect for the first year of operation 2011 for both cases (15-min measurements and averaged data over 1h).

Lagging between the time that the datalogger records the irradiance and ambient temperature measurements from amorphous and the time where it registers power values from the inverter connected to p-Si may be the cause because it' can not be perfectly synchronized: the measurements are not taken at the same moment and they might be sent to the datalogger storing the data at different times. Hence, data cleaning has been done to avoid this synchronization, however it still present in 2014,2015 and 2016.

4. Constraints:

The most important scope limitation is that we have lack of available data measurements. Some constraints are present as well:

- We have atmospheric data only for amorphous modules. We recover this data for polycrystalline from amorphous. However, we still have a problem of synchronization between electrical and atmospheric measurements for poly-Si modules for 2014,2015 and 2016.
- We don't have module temperature. We used the NOCT Model to calculate it using measurements of irradiance and ambient temperature.
- For low irradiance (under $200\text{W}/\text{m}^2$) the inverter is malfunctioning. Therefore, the faults diagnosis is only based on data for $G > 200\text{W}/\text{m}^2$.
- The available measurements don't include DC current, so we can't use the simple non-linear regression to obtain the parameters of single-Diode-Model. We used particular conditions and solve the system of non-linear equation to extract these parameters

- The available measurements don't include I-V characteristics. Therefore, we don't have the measured DC power, we have only the measured AC power. Hence, we should simulate the AC production and make some assumptions: Evans & PVUSA models normally simulate the production at DC side. However, the fitted coefficients of these models used regression with AC measurements assuming that inverter efficiency is constant. Therefore, we should simulate inverter efficiency to modelize the AC power output using the SDM, because SDM provides only the power at DC side.

The constraints of this thesis may affect the precision of the results. Due to time constraints, the simulation of solar panels has been largely based on existing data streams.

Chapter 4: Modeling and Identification of PV modules parameters

This chapter represents the core of this thesis. It analyzes the methodology and the different ways adopted in the identification of the parameters of each of the three models that were previously explained in chapter 2. The models investigated are the **Electrical Model (SDM) with 4 or 5 parameters**, **Evans Model** and the **empirical Model (PVUSA)**. The models were trained using Matlab script.

We will present the equations and the conditions of simulations adopted in each model, and validate the results by comparing our results with the values found in the literature or provided by manufacturer's datasheets. The errors between the measured output power and the modeled one will be studied in the next chapter over the evaluation period (from 2011 to 2016) for each technology and for each model.

It's important to notice that only hourly averages measurements were used to run the models of the power production.

1. Modelization and Identification of the parameters of PV panels

a) Global approach for estimating unknown parameters of each model

The flowchart shown in Fig 22 attempts to present the approach adopted to evaluate the parameters of each model at different conditions, depending on the model. It starts by describing the manufacturer's datasheet and the constants needed as inputs. Then, the atmospheric data (G, T_{amb}) processed is loaded to calculate the module temperature and to study the different operating point (G, T_{mod}).

Once we have (G, T_{mod}), we can choose the model we want to work with: Electrical Model (Single Diode Model with 4 or 5 parameters); Evans Model or Empirical Model (PVUSA).

Figure22: Parameter Estimation approaches for each model

Let's start by the **Electrical Model**. It's important to notice that we have 3 cases: **SDM with 5 parameters manually adjusted to our STC measurements**; **SDM with 4 parameters extracted** and **SDM with 5 parameters extracted analytically and numerically**.

To extract the 4 or 5 parameters, depending on whether we will take into account the shunt resistance or not, we implement simple set of non-linear equations at particular conditions (OC, SC, MPP, slope of the I-V curve at OC and SC), the parameters can

be determined analytically (for SDM with 4 parameters) and numerically (for SDM with 5 parameters) by the manufacturer's datasheets ($I_{sc,STC}, V_{oc,STC}, I_{mpp,STC}, V_{mpp,STC}, P_{mpp,STC}$) feeded as inputs in the MATLAB programming, which make the process fast and accurate.

Once the parameters at STC are extracted, they can be evaluated at different operating point (G, T_{mod}) to calculate the current delivered by each panel of the PV installation, at each operating point. Hence, the I-V curve is built in each operating point (G, T_{mod}) for the two technologies to calculate the Maximum power output at given irradiance and module temperature, which is the DC simulated power output $P_{mpp,sim}$.

To validate the model (with 3 cases), the I-V & P-V curves are computed at STC, at different module temperature and at different solar irradiance. Then, a comparison between the I-V & P-V curves simulations and the calculation of V_{oc} and I_{sc} results obtained for each PV module technology tested in outdoors conditions has been carried out.

An alternative approach, with the aim to reduce the complexity of calculation, it is based on **Evans Model**. Small amount of information is needed to calculate the DC output power, which is normally provided by the manufacturer. However, this model is based on a parametric approach to model the PV system efficiency. To obtain the 3 unknown parameters, we used 2 conditions of simulations based on filtering the low and high values of irradiance and module temperature, then, we fit the model equation with measurement data. As the measurements are taken only at AC side, the efficiency modeled is at AC side, which means it takes into account the inverter efficiency which is assumed constant. Therefore, the production modeled is at the AC side $P_{ac,sim}$.

To validate the model, the regression results of the parameters are compared to the values given by the manufacturer and found in the literature.

The third model used in this study is the **Empirical Model (PVUSA)**, based only on data points (G, T_{amb}). With the same assumption as we used with Evans Model, the 3 parameters parameters are found by filtering the constant values of G and T_{amb} and by fitting the model equation with measurement data. As the power measured is provided at the AC side, hence the power of the module takes into account the inverter efficiency which is assumed constant. Therefore, the production modeled is at the AC side $P_{ac,sim}$. To validate the model, the results are compared to the values given by the manufacturer by an approach similar to the Evans Model.

It's important to notice that the fitted parameters of Evans and PVUSA are fitted only with the measurements of the year 2011, and will be fixed for all the coming years. For Electrical model (SDM), we don't need historical data measurements because we don't make regression technique, but we used particular conditions using the key points of the I-V curve.

These models were already described in chapter but in order to better understand this review, here is a quick overview of the models used in our study to simulate the production of the PV system installed at IUT of Cachan, France.

The following paragraphs describe more in details the conditions of simulation adopted in each model to obtain the unknown parameters of each model.

b) Identification of the 4 or 5 unknown reference parameters of the Single-Diode-Model

The current delivered by the panel is express as: $I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{aV_t}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V + IR_s}{R_p}$; $V_t = N_s \frac{kT}{q}$ **(eq1)**

As explained in chapter 2, the current delivered by the panel depends on some parameters that need to be determined; the photo-current source I_{ph} , the ideality factor a , the saturation current I_0 , and the series and parallel resistances R_s and R_p respectively of a PV module [16][17].

But for evaluating these parameters at different operating point, manufacturer given output characteristics ($I_{ph,STC}, I_{0,STC}, a_{STC}, R_{s,STC}, R_{p,STC}$) are required. Generally, manufacturers don't provide these unknown parameters at STC. Thus, we should find a way to extract these parameters.

i. Case1: SDM-5 parameters identified from literature fixed & adjusted with STC measurements

Many authors have proposed the lower bound and the upper bound of the parameters ($I_{ph,STC}, a_{STC}, I_{0,STC}, R_{s,STC}$ and $R_{p,STC}$) that compose various PV models [24].

The value of **the photo current** is approximately equal to the value of $I_{sc,STC}$ (ideal case), which can be used as a good guess value. Usually, **the diode quality factor** takes a value between 1 and 2 as it is reported in literature, being near 1 at high currents, rising towards 2 at low currents. **The reverse saturation current** guess value can be obtained by evaluating eq1 at OC assuming $R_p \rightarrow \infty$. It takes a value between 10^{-10} and 1 A. A guess value for **serie resistance** can be obtained by evaluating at open circuit condition. It takes a value between 0.01 to 10 Ω . The **shunt resistance** takes a value between 10 Ω to infinite [24].

We tried to find the values that was able to give the same results provided by the manufacturer ($P_{mpp}, V_{mpp}, I_{mpp}, V_{oc}, I_{sc}$). The values of the constants, adjusted with STC datasheet, are shown in the section of parameters identification results (table 11).

ii. Case2: SDM-4 parameters identified using particular conditions

For simplification purpose, the parallel resistance is assumed infinite, and can be neglected [16]. So the last term $\frac{V + IR_s}{R_p}$ is eliminated in this model for the further work (next case). Therefore, this simple model has a photocurrent source, a single diode junction and a series resistance (Figure 12-(b)).

It means we have 4 unknown parameters: ($I_{ph,STC}, I_{0,STC}, a_{STC}, R_{s,STC}$)

The current delivered by the panel is: $I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{aV_t}\right) - 1 \right]$ **(eq2)**

The idea is to estimate the parameters analytically by means of equation at extreme points of the I-V curve. By applying three remarkable conditions i.e. open-circuit ($I=0, V=V_{oc,STC}$), short-circuit ($I = I_{sc,STC}, V = 0$), the maximum power point condition ($I = I_{mpp,STC}, V = V_{mpp,STC}$) to eq2 at standard test condition, the following equations can be derived:

- At short circuit condition: $I_{sc,STC} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp \left(\frac{I_{sc,STC} R_s, STC}{a_{STC} V_t, STC} \right) - 1 \right]$ **(eq3)**

- At open circuit condition: $0 = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp \left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC} V_t, STC} \right) - 1 \right]$ **(eq4)**

- At maximum power point condition: $I_{mpp,STC} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + I_{mpp,STC} R_s, STC}{a_{STC} V_t, STC} \right) - 1 \right]$ **(eq5)**

Evaluation of the photo current:

In the ideal case, the current delivered by the panel can be written as [15]: $I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp \left(\frac{V}{aV_t} \right) - 1 \right]$

Applying the **short circuit condition (eq3)**: $I_{sc,STC} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} [\exp(0) - 1] = I_{ph,STC}$

This equality is valid only in the ideal case. In reality, when the cell is short circuited, negligible current flows in the diode. Hence the proportionality constant $I_{ph,STC}$ is set so the rated short circuit current I_{sc} at is delivered under rated irradiation ($1000W/m^2$).

The relationship between the photocurrent and irradiance is linear: $I_{ph,STC} = I_{sc,STC} \frac{G}{G_{STC}}$ hence, at STC: $I_{ph,STC} = I_{sc,STC}$

Evaluation of the saturation current:

Applying the open circuit condition (eq4): When the cell is open circuited and illuminated, the photocurrent flows entirely in the diode:

$$I_{0,STC} = \frac{I_{ph,STC}}{\exp \left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC} V_t, STC} \right) - 1}$$

Evaluation of the ideality constant:

In the proposed method, the maximum power point at STC is considered for evaluating ‘a’ using the property $\frac{dP}{dV} = 0$ at the maximum power point: $P=VI$; $\frac{dP}{dV} = I \frac{dV}{dV} + V \frac{dI}{dV} = 0$

By applying the MPP condition: $\left(\frac{dI}{dV} \right)_{MPP} + \frac{I_{mpp}}{V_{mpp}} = 0$

By differentiating the equation: $I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) - 1 \right] - I_{mpp} = 0$

$$\frac{dI}{dV} = \frac{\left(\frac{dI}{dV} \right)_{MPP}}{\left(\frac{dI}{dI} \right)_{MPP}} = \frac{-\frac{I_0}{aV_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right)}{-\frac{I_0 R_s}{aV_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) - 1}$$

Asplying the MPP condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{dI}{dV} \right)_{MPP} &= \frac{\left(\frac{dI}{dV} \right)_{MPP}}{\left(\frac{dI}{dI} \right)_{MPP}} = \frac{-\frac{I_0}{aV_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right)}{-\frac{I_0 R_s}{aV_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) - 1} = -\frac{I_{mpp}}{V_{mpp}} \\ &\frac{-\frac{I_0}{aV_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right)}{\frac{I_0 R_s}{aV_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) + 1} - \frac{I_{mpp}}{V_{mpp}} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

By multiplying and dividing by a:

$$\frac{-V_{mpp} \left[\frac{I_0}{V_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) \right] - I_{mpp} \left[\frac{I_0 R_s}{V_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) \right] - a I_{mpp}}{V_{mpp} \left[\frac{I_0 R_s}{V_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) + a \right]} = 0$$

$$\frac{a I_{mpp} + (I_{mpp} R_s - V_{mpp}) \left[\frac{I_0}{V_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) \right]}{V_{mpp} \left[\frac{I_0 R_s}{V_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) + a \right]} = 0$$

For this equation to be valid, the numerator must be zero as the denominator is finite:

$$a I_{mpp} + (I_{mpp} R_s - V_{mpp}) \left[\frac{I_0}{V_t} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I_{mpp} R_s}{aV_t} \right) \right] = 0$$

When writing at STC, the equation becomes:

$$a I_{mpp,STC} + \left[\frac{I_{0,STC}}{V_t,STC} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + I_{mpp,STC} R_s,STC}{a_{STC} V_t,STC} \right) \right] (I_{mpp,STC} R_s - V_{mpp,STC}) = 0 \quad \text{(eq6)}$$

By applying the MPP condition at STC to: $I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp \left(\frac{V + I R_s}{aV_t} \right) - 1 \right]$

And rearranging terms, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \exp \left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + I_{mpp,STC} R_s,STC}{a_{STC} V_t,STC} \right) &= \frac{I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC} + I_{0,STC}}{I_{0,STC}} \\ R_s &= \frac{a_{STC} V_t,STC \ln \left(\frac{I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC} + I_{0,STC}}{I_{0,STC}} \right) - V_{mpp,STC}}{I_{mpp,STC}} \end{aligned}$$

By combining and substituting these equations, we can replace the terms $(I_{mpp,STC}R_s - V_{mpp,STC})$; $\exp\left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC}+I_{mpp,STC}R_s,STC}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right)$ and $I_{0,STC}$ in the eq6, we obtain:

$$aI_{mpp,STC} + \left[I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC} + \frac{I_{sc,STC}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1} \right] \left[\frac{I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC} + \frac{I_{sc,STC}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1} - \frac{2V_{mpp,STC}}{V_{t,STC}} \right]$$

When the data given in the manufacturer's datasheets are used, the left hand side of the equation becomes a function of "a" and it is denoted by $f(a)$:

$$f(a) = aI_{mpp,STC} + \left[I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC} + \frac{I_{sc,STC}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1} \right] \left[\frac{I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC} + \frac{I_{sc,STC}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1} - \frac{2V_{mpp,STC}}{V_{t,STC}} \right] = 0$$

Thus, 'a' is found by solving $f(a)=0$ as shown in fig 23.

Figure23: Graph of $f(a)$ vs « a » for p-Si modules (left) & a-Si modules (right) with Zoomed view of the zero crossing point

According to fig 23, $a=1.73$ becomes the solution for polycrystalline modules. And $a=3.92$ for amorphous modules.

One thing that may pop up to the reader's eye is that the ideality factor of amorphous is very high. The literature states that it takes a value between 1 and 2 (though can in some cases be higher) [6]. As explained in chapter 2, the four parameters model assumes that the slope of the I-V curve is flat at the short-circuit condition: $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=0} = 0$. However, this assumption is not generally valid for amorphous PV systems [26]. The short circuit I-V slope is finite and negative. However, we will test the results of amorphous to make further comparison, we took $a=3$.

The values of « a » for polycrystalline technology is widely accepted; the knowledge of its exact value is pointless in this work because it gives rise to very little difference in the final I-V curve behavior. This way, only the serie resistance remain to be estimated.

Evaluation of serie resistance:

The series resistance of the panel has a large impact on the slope of the I-V curve at $V = V_{oc}$. Evaluating at $V = V_{oc}$, and rearranging in terms of R_s [19]:

$$\text{with } X_v = \frac{I_{0,STC}}{aV_{t,STC}} * \exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{aV_{t,STC}}\right)$$

$$R_s = -\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=V_{oc}} - \frac{1}{X_v}$$

The slope in OC is not directly provided, it can be approximated by plotting the points, provided by the manufacturer's datasheet and determining the slope between the OC and the MPP.

Hence, in the I-V curve, between $(0, V_{oc})$ and (I_{mpp}, V_{mpp}) : $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=V_{oc}} = -\frac{1}{R_{s,0}} = \frac{0 - I_{mpp,STC}}{V_{oc,STC} - V_{mpp,STC}}$

This value should be divided by two in order to obtain a reasonable slope value.

By differentiating the equation: $I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V+IR_s}{aV_t}\right) - 1 \right] - I = 0$

By evaluating at $V = V_{oc}$, and rearranging in terms of R_s :

$$\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=V_{oc}} = \frac{-\frac{I_0}{aV_t} \exp\left(\frac{V_{oc}}{aV_t}\right)}{-\frac{I_0 R_s}{aV_t} \exp\left(\frac{V_{oc}}{aV_t}\right) - 1} = -\frac{1}{R_{s,0}} = \frac{0 - I_{mpp,STC}}{V_{oc,STC} - V_{mpp,STC}}$$

$$\text{Hence: } R_{s,0} = R_{s,STC} = \frac{\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC} - V_{mpp,STC}}{I_{mpp,STC}}\right)}{2} - \frac{1}{\frac{I_{0,STC}}{aV_{t,STC}} * \exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{aV_{t,STC}}\right)}$$

Using the values obtained from manufacturer's datasheet, 4 parameters were calculated. The parameters identification results are shown in (table 11).

iii. Case3: SDM-5 parameters identified using particular conditions

The five parameters I_{ph}, a, I_0, R_s and R_p of a PV module (Figure 12-(c)) are calculated with the aid of five equations that can be

solved numerically and simultaneously.

Several researches exist in literature about the calculation of these parameters to build the mathematical and numerical model of the PV module. This study considers a simulation procedure different than the one proposed by some authors.

In this study, we perform parameters extraction by using the **Levenberg-Marquardt optimization algorithm (LMA)**, a robust algorithm which, in many cases, converges to a solution even if the starting point is far from the true minimum [40]. The basic idea is to estimate the initial values of the five parameters ($I_{ph,STC}$, a_{STC} , $I_{0,STC}$, $R_{s,STC}$ and $R_{p,STC}$) analytically by the mean of equations at OC, SC, slope of the I-V curve and using the fill factor. The starting estimate $X_0 = [I_{ph,0}, I_0, a_0, R_{s,0}, R_{p,0}]$ can be refined using iterations.

After having expressed the initial values, a system of 5 non-linear equations is needed to solve the 5 unknown parameters. The system of 5 equations is specified by $F(x)=0$ where $F(x)$ is a function that returns a vector value and X is the vector of unknown parameters $X = [I_{ph,STC}, I_{0,STC}, a_{STC}, R_{s,STC}, R_{p,STC}] = [x(1), x(2), x(3), x(4), x(5)]$.

Afterwards, the simultaneous equation can be easily solved in MATLAB with Newton-Raphson technique using fsolve symbolic function available in MATLAB optimization toolbox [40], setting the Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm (LMA) as a solver method [6][41]. It converges quickly especially if the iteration begins sufficiently near the desired root.

❖ Identifying initial values & boundaries of the module parameters:

Initial value of the ideality factor:

The FF is a measure of the "squareness" of the IV curve. And as said in the literature review (chapter 2-modeling section), that the ideality factor has an impact on the I-V curve and degrades the FF.

The FF value falls between the $0.65 < FF < 1$ interval. Thus, the initial value for the ideality factor can be taken as [42]:

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{FF} = \frac{I_{sc,STC} V_{oc,STC}}{I_{mpp,STC} V_{mpp,STC}}$$

The initial value of serie resistance:

The slope in OC is not directly provided, it can be approximated by plotting the points, provided by the manufacturer's datasheet and determining the slope between the OC and the MPP.

Hence, in the I-V curve, between $(0, V_{oc})$ and (I_{mpp}, V_{mpp}) : $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{V=V_{oc}} = -\frac{1}{R_{s,0}} = \frac{0 - I_{mpp,STC}}{V_{oc,STC} - V_{mpp,STC}}$

Hence:
$$R_{s,0} = \frac{\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC} - V_{mpp,STC}}{I_{mpp,STC}}\right)}{2}$$

The initial value of parallel resistance:

The slope in SC is not directly provided, it can be approximated by plotting the points, provided by the manufacturer's datasheet and determining the slope between the SC and the MPP.

Hence, in the I-V curve, between $(I_{sc}, 0)$ and (I_{mpp}, V_{mpp}) : $\left(\frac{dI}{dV}\right)_{I=I_{sc}} = -\frac{1}{R_{p,0}} = \frac{I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC}}{0 - V_{mpp,STC}}$

Hence:
$$R_{p,0} = \frac{\left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC}}{I_{sc,STC} - I_{mpp,STC}}\right)}{2}$$

Initial value of the photo-current:

By applying the OC condition, and rearranging terms, we obtain:
$$I_{ph,0} = I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_0 V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{oc,STC}}{R_{p,0}}$$

Initial value of the saturation current:

By applying the SC condition, we obtain:
$$I_{sc,STC} = I_{ph,0} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{I_{sc,STC} R_{s,0}}{a_0 V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{I_{sc,STC} R_{s,0}}{R_{p,0}}$$

By replacing $I_{ph,0}$ and rearranging terms, we obtain:

$$I_0 = \frac{\left[I_{sc,STC} - \left(\frac{V_{oc,STC} - I_{sc,STC} R_{s,0}}{R_{p,0}} \right) \right]}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_0 V_{t,STC}}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{I_{sc,STC} R_{s,0}}{a_0 V_{t,STC}}\right)}$$

Unlike, lsqcurvefit function, in fsolve function, we can't set the lower and the upper bound.

But starting with $X_0 = [I_{ph,0}, I_0, \frac{a_0}{0.8}, \frac{R_{s,0}}{100}, (R_{p,0} * 1000)]$ for polycrystalline modules; and with $X_0 = [I_{ph,0}, I_0, \frac{a_0}{0.8}, \frac{R_{s,0}}{9.5}, (R_{p,0} * 100000)]$ for amorphous modules; as initial guess of the vector of unknown parameters X and after the best-fit procedure, the errors due to the initial approximation are reduced.

The estimates X is determined by means of a best-fit that minimizes the objective function $\|F\|$, which is defined by: $F(x)=I-$

$$\left[x(1) - x(2) * \left[\exp\left(\frac{V+x(4)*I}{x(3)*V_t}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V+x(4)*I}{x(5)} \right]$$

❖ The System of five non-linear equations:

From I-V characteristic of PV modules, at extreme points, from equation of I:

- At open circuit condition, at STC: $I=0$; $V=V_{oc}$
$$0 = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,STC}}{a_{STC} V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{oc,STC}}{R_{p,STC}}$$
- At short circuit condition, at STC: $I=I_{sc}$; $V=0$
$$I_{sc,STC} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp\left(\frac{I_{sc,STC} R_{s,STC}}{a_{STC} V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{I_{sc,STC} R_{s,STC}}{R_{p,STC}}$$
- At maximum power point condition, at STC: $I=I_{mpp}$; $V=V_{mpp}$
$$I_{mpp,STC} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + I_{mpp,STC} R_{s,STC}}{a_{STC} V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{mpp,STC} + I_{mpp,STC} R_{s,STC}}{R_{p,STC}}$$

We have five unknowns, and until now we only have 3 equations. So we need 2 more equations.

From I-V characteristic of PV modules (figure 24), we can establish these 2 equations at $\frac{MPP}{2}$ points $\frac{I_{mpp}}{2}$ and $\frac{V_{mpp}}{2}$. The graph below explains the key points proposed :

Figure24: Key points proposed of an I-V curve

- At $\frac{V_{MPP}}{2}$ point ($I=I'_1$; $V=\frac{V_{mpp}}{2}$):
$$I'_1 = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{mpp} + I'_1 R_s}{a V_t}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{mpp} + I'_1 R_s}{R_p}$$

$$I'_1 = I_1 + \frac{I_{sc} - I_1}{2} \quad ; \quad I_1 = a \frac{V_{mpp}}{2} + b \quad \begin{cases} a = \frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} = \frac{I_{mpp} - I_{sc}}{V_{mpp} - 0} \\ b = I_{sc} \end{cases}$$

By substituting these equations, we obtain: $I'_1 = \frac{I_{mpp} + 3I_{sc}}{4}$

By replacing I'_1 and applying STC:

$$\frac{I_{mpp,STC} + 3I_{sc,STC}}{4} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + \left(\frac{I_{mpp,STC} + 3I_{sc,STC}}{4}\right)R_{s,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{mpp,STC} + \left(\frac{I_{mpp,STC} + 3I_{sc,STC}}{4}\right)R_{s,STC}}{R_{p,STC}}$$

- At $\frac{I_{MPP}}{2}$ point ($I=\frac{I_{mpp}}{2}$; $V=V'_1$):
$$\frac{I_{mpp}}{2} = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V'_1 + \frac{I_{mpp}}{2}R_s}{a V_t}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V'_1 + \frac{I_{mpp}}{2}R_s}{R_p}$$

$$V'_1 = V_1 + \frac{V_{oc} - V_1}{2} \quad ; \quad V_1 = a' \frac{V_{mpp}}{2} + b' \quad \begin{cases} a' = \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta I} = \frac{V_{mpp} - V_{oc}}{I_{mpp} - 0} \\ b' = V_{oc} \end{cases}$$

By substituting these equations, we obtain: $V'_1 = \frac{V_{mpp} + 3V_{oc}}{4}$

By replacing V'_1 and applying STC:

$$\frac{I_{mpp,STC}}{2} = I_{ph,STC} - I_{0,STC} \left[\exp\left(\frac{\left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + 3V_{oc,STC}}{4}\right) + \frac{I_{mpp,STC}}{2}R_{s,STC}}{a_{STC}V_{t,STC}}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{\left(\frac{V_{mpp,STC} + 3V_{oc,STC}}{4}\right) + \frac{I_{mpp,STC}}{2}R_{s,STC}}{R_{p,STC}}$$

All of the constants in the above equations can be determined by using the manufacturers datasheet. The parameters identification results are shown in (table 11).

iv. Reference Parameter identification results of the 3 cases

The results of the parameters estimated in each case are presented in table 11:

Table11: SDM Parameters estimation results

Electrical Parameters at STC $G=1000W/m^2$; $T_{mod}=25^\circ C$	Polycrystalline			Amorphous		
	SDM-5 param-literature	4 parameters extracted	SDM-5 parameters extracted	SDM-5 param-literature	4 parameters extracted	SDM-5 parameters extracted
I_{ph_STC} (A)	5.39	5.39	5.34	6.6	6.6	6.6
I_0_STC (A)	3.13e-06	4.75e-06	2.47e-06	9.85E-03	0.02	3.33E-03
a_STC	1.68	1.73	1.65	2.5	3	2.14
R_s_STC (ohm)	0.3	0.24	0.06	0.1	(-0.06)	0.12
R_p_STC (ohm)	300	Infinite	82500	800	Infinite	1244604.31

For **poly-Si**, the computed parameters using four-or five-parameter models considering STC are consistent with literature. For **amorphous**, the infinite value of the shunt resistance for the four-parameter model is undoubtedly a source of inaccuracy. We obtain high value of “a” and negative resistance. It confirms what the literature states: the model with 4 parameters is not valid for amorphous [26], it's not important since we'll not use it in our study. However, the results obtained with the 5-parameters (extracted) model are acceptable.

Fig 25 shows the I-V and P-V curves for the SCHOTT polycrystalline and amorphous plotted at $T_{STC} = 25^\circ C$; $G_{STC} = 1000 W/m^2$ of the case 3 “SDM 5-parameters extracted”. We are not presenting the I-V&P-V curves of the case 1 and 2 because they are irrelevant for our present work (See Appendice D).

Figure25 : I-V & P-V curves of Poly (above) & Amorphous (below) 5-parameters extracted at STC

For **poly**, all the points are matched as expected. For **amorphous**, some points (P_{mpp} , V_{mpp} , I_{mpp}) are not exactly matched which may be attributed to non-perfect translation equations. However, it is acceptable.

To validate the parameters results, the relative error (RE) is calculated. RE is defined as the mean absolute difference between the STC values and computed current/voltage/power values of the I-V curves for given temperature & irradiance points.

The relative error calculated in this section is expressed as [20]: $RE = \frac{|X_{STC} - X_{sim}|}{X_{STC}} * 100$

Table12 : Parameters estimation validation for poly-Si

Parameters at STC G=1000W/m ² ; Tmod=25°C	Polycrystalline						
	Manufacturers' specifications	SDM Models results			Relative Error (%)		
		5 param-literature	4 param extracted	5param extracted	SDM-5 param-literature	4 parameters extracted	SDM-5parameters extracted
Pmpp_STC (W)	179.685	179.03	175.06	179.65	0.36	2.57	0.02
Vmpp_STC (V)	36.3	35.51	35.51	36.49	2.18	2.17	0.52
Impp_STC (A)	4.95	5.04	4.93	4.92	1.82	0.40	0.61
Voc_STC (V)	44.6	44.6	44.6	44.6	0	0	0
Isc_STC (A)	5.39	5.39	5.39	5.39	0	0	0

For **poly-Si**, the maximum errors occur for four-parameter model, as it can be noticed on table 12. It is to be expected because parallel resistance plays the dominant role in determining the shape of I-V and P-V curves and is kept infinite for this case. In general, REs for the five-parameter models (literature and extracted) are lesser than those of the four-parameter model. Especially, the five-parameter model extracted strongly agrees to measurements at STC. The results show that the RE on peak-power voltage is 0.52%, the RE on peak power is 0.02% and the RE on peak current is 0.61%. Therefore, the RE is less than 1% for poly in term of power, voltage and current.

Table13: Parameters estimation validation for a-Si

Parameters at STC G=1000W/m ² ; Tmod=25°C	Amorphous						
	Manufacturers' specifications	SDM Models results			Relative Error (%)		
		5 param-literature	4 param extracted	5param extracted	SDM-5 param-literature	4 parameters extracted	SDM-5param extracted
Pmpp_STC (W)	90.133	90.71	89.05	94.7	0.64	1.20	5.07
Vmpp_STC (V)	17.3	16.73	16.81	17.03	3.29	2.83	1.56
Impp_STC (A)	5.21	5.42	5.29	5.56	4.03	1.53	6.72
Voc_STC (V)	23.4	23.4	23.4	23.4	0	0	0
Isc_STC (A)	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.6	0	0	0

For **amorphous**, it can be seen that, despite the modeling curves do not match STC data in all points (P_{mpp} , V_{mpp} , I_{mpp}) for the 5 parameters extracted (figure 25); however the 5 parameters model adjusted (literature) is closer to the datasheet data than

the four-parameter. And minor RE occurs at STC and for the five-parameter model (literature). The 5-parameter model is not exactly matched with manufacturers' specifications (the RE is less than 7% in term of power, voltage and current), which may be attributed to non-perfect translation equations. Although, it is sufficiently acceptable for majority points.

v. PV module parameters at real conditions of work

To verify the relevance of this set of values, it is necessary to compute the I-V & P-V curves at given (G, T_{mod}) resulting from these parameters as shown on figs 26, 27. We are not presenting the I-V & P-V curves of the case 1 and 2 because they are irrelevant for our present work (Appendice D).

Case3: I-V & P-V curves of Poly & Amorphous 5-param extracted:

For $G=[1200, 1000, 800, 600, 400, 200] W/m^2$ and $T_{mod} = 25^{\circ}C$:

Fig 26 shows the I-V & P-V curves for polycrystallines and amorphous modules respectively for different ranges of irradiance from $200 W/m^2$ to $1200 W/m^2$ at $25^{\circ}C$. The panels are held at a constant module temperature.

Figure 26: I-V & P-V curves of Poly & Amorphous 5-parameters extracted at different G and $25^{\circ}C$

On observing the I-V curves we see that with increase in irradiance G values, PV module current I_{sc} value also increases proportionally but PV module voltage V_{oc} increases logarithmically with G.

For $T_{mod}=[60\ 45\ 35\ 25\ 20]^{\circ}C$; $G=1000W/m^2$

The accuracy of the SDM-5 parameters extracted model was tested for different levels of module temperature. All simulations were performed at $1000 W/m^2$ (Figure 27).

Figure27: I-V & P-V curves of Poly & Amorphous 5-parameters extracted at different Tmod and 1000W/m²

It can be seen that 5-parameters extracted model accurately computed the I- V curves of both modules technologies for various temperature levels. However, simulation is better for polycrystalline than the amorphous technologies.

It is observed that as temperature increases PV module current I_{sc} also increases slightly and PV module voltage shows significant decrease in its value. The temperature is inversely proportional to the voltage V_{oc} . Also, with increase in temperature, output power decreases.

We observe for the 3 cases (Case 1 and Case 2 are in Appendice D) a similar drop in current when the irradiance is lower for both technologies, and similar drop in voltage when the module temperature increases, which translates into a drop in power. This result was expected since all solar cells from our panels deliver a current proportional to the irradiance and voltage proportionnel to temperature [20].

vi. Summary and validation of results

To validate the 3 cases of the electrical model, a comparison between the simulation (V_{oc} and I_{sc} of the computed I-V & P-V curves) and calculation ($V_{oc,cal}$ and $I_{sc,cal}$ from equations presented below) results for each technology has been carried out.

The short-circuit current I_{sc} varies nonlinearly with irradiance and its variation with temperature is fairly small depending on its temperature coefficient. There are different common methods to express variations of the short-circuit current I_{sc} with irradiance and module temperature. In the method chosen for our study, the short-circuit current is expressed in terms, of G and T_{mod} , using the following linear empirical relation [20]:

$$I_{sc,cal}(G, T_{mod}) = [I_{sc,STC} + K_i(T_{mod} - T_{STC})] \frac{G}{G_{STC}}$$

The open-circuit voltage V_{oc} exhibits a strong dependence on temperature, which is described by the voltage temperature coefficient. Its dependence on insolation G is, however, not very significant and follows a logarithmic function. Different methods of expressing V_{oc} as a function of T_{mod} and G have been reported in many articles. In the method chosen for our study and explained below, the dependence on insolation is neglected [20]:

$$V_{oc,cal}(T_{mod}) = V_{oc,STC} + K_v(T_{mod} - T_{STC})$$

The relative error calculated in this section is expressed as:

$$RE = \frac{|X_{cal} - X_{sim}|}{X_{cal}} * 100$$

The value of V_{oc} and I_{sc} simulated at different T_{mod} and at differend G for both technologies are presented in appendice D.

Results show, for both technologies, that whenever temperature increase it leads to decreases the open circuit voltage V_{oc} and slightly increasing the short circuit current I_{sc} . It was also demonstrated that as irradiance increases I_{sc} increases and V_{oc} increases slightly. Results indicate an average RE less than 1% in almost all points except for amorphous when varying the temperature. For amorphous, we observe (See appendice D) that V_{oc} simulated drastically decreases with T_{mod} , we found an average RE less than 12%.

Finally, the simulations of the I-V & P-V curves, using Matlab generated values that matched very well with calculated values using the equations above and then we were able to continue the actual work.

Concluding remarks about the behavior of the power with G and T_{mod} :

To see if the electrical model (SDM) agree with measurements, we filter first the weird behavior of the inverter at $G < 200W/m^2$, and then we plot the power simulated and measured as function of G and T_{mod} , using **the five parameters extracted by particular conditions** (figure 28, 29):

Figure28: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for poly-Si using fitted coefficients of SDM Model (outdoor conditions)

Figure29: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for amorphous using fitted coefficients of SDM Model (outdoor conditions)

As can be seen in figure 28, for poly-Si in the first year of operation (2011), SDM-5parameters (extracted) model agree with the measurements (year 2011) regardless of G and T_{amb} . The SDM-5 parameters model is validated for poly-Si.

However, for amorphous, we have strange behavior at high value of irradiance and ambient temperature. The SDM-5parameters (extracted) model and the data measurements of 2011 don't follow strong linear relationship. According to the results of SDM-5 parameters, the amorphous PV system produces more than it should at high G (700-900W/m²) and medium T_{amb} (25-40°C). This is due to the fact that the electrical model depends on parameters (I_{ph} , I_0 , a , R_s , R_p) that depend also on on G and T_{mod} (calculated by G and T_{amb} by NOCT model) as shown in table 4 in chapter 2. When G and T_{amb} increase, these parameters are affected and hence impact the current delivered by the panel, which impact the power simulated by the SDM-5parameters. As can be seen, there is a gap between the simulated and measured power. The deviations are more pronounced for high G and T_{amb} . The undershot part of the plots means that we obtain positif Mean Bias Error (MBE) between measurements and model for high G or T_{amb} . In other words, $P_{ac,meas} > P_{ac,sim}$ at high G and T_{amb} .

Therefore, results are not accurate for amorphous and may affect the precision of the results. It is no doubt that there is a problem in the extraction of the parameters of amorphous, especially in the factor ideality, which is found equal to 2.14. Due to time constraints and since the problem is only related to the factor of ideality, and the others 4 parameters are properly extracted, we changed only the factor ideality of amorphous and we tried with a value of $a=1.5$ and plot $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G & T_{amb} :

Figure30: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for amorphous using fitted coefficients of SDM Model with $a=1.5$

As can be seen in figure 30, for amorphous in the first year of operation (2011), SDM-5 parameters (extracted) model agree with the measurements (year 2011) regardless of G and T_{amb} , which validate now the electrical model for the two technologies.

The graphs of the simulated and measured power output with G and T_{amb} , for both technologies, for the other years of evaluation is presented in chapter 5.

vii. The case chosen for the simulation

The four- and five-parameters models used to simulate the DC production of poly-Si and amorphous modules for various operating conditions are done in this section.

The main conclusions from the analysis of the evaluation of electrical parameters and fitting of the I-V and P-V curves of both modules are:

- R_p plays an important role. It was seen that the RE between manufacturer specifications and results of SDM-5 parameters model was less than the one with SDM-4 parameters model.
- Most parameters depend on both the module temperature and the solar irradiance. Thus, the mastery of their behavior is crucial to correctly simulate the performance of the PV module.

As was indicated by the RE values, both the four-parameters (see AppendicesD) and five- parameter models accurately fit data at STC of PV modules used for various operating conditions analyzed. However, completed **five- parameter model extracted** with analytical and numerical calculation of parameters yields more accurate current, voltage and power than the simplified four-parameter model because it involves less approximations because it takes into account the effect of R_p .

c) Identification of the 3 unknown parameters of the Evans Model

This section is devoted to a simplified procedure for calculating power output starting with a minimum of input information: datasheets and atmospheric data. However, this model doesn't provide I-V and P-V curves.

i. Fitted Coefficients Method:

As explained in chapter 2, the model is based on a parametric approach to model the PV efficiency [28]:

$$\eta = \eta_{fit} \left[1 + K_{p,fit}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \nu_{fit} \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right) \right]$$

And the AC production simulated is expressed as [27][28]:

$$P_{ac,sim} = \eta_{fit} \left[1 + K_{p,fit}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \nu_{fit} \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right) \right] * G * N_{mod,s} * S_u$$

η_{fit} , $K_{p,fit}$, ν_{fit} are the 3 unknown parameters obtained by filtering the data and fitting the model equation with measurement data. As the efficiency measured is provided at the AC side, hence the efficiency of the module fitted takes into account the inverter efficiency $\eta_{fit} = \eta_{PV,sim} \eta_{inv,sim}$ and the inverter efficiency $\eta_{inv,sim}$ is assumed constant.

It important to note that these parameters are extracted only for the first year of evaluation (from April 2011 to December 2011) with only hourly averages measurements.

Evaluation of this model was done by performing conditions of fit. The resulting equations were then used to estimate the parameters. The obtained values will be fixed for the other years.

❖ **Conditions of fit 1- Filtering the low solar irradiance & low module temperature to get the coefficient of irradiance ν_{fit} :** $T_{mod}=[20;30]^{\circ}C$; $G=[150,400]W/m^2$

After calculating the module temperature, we filter the low insolation (0-400W/m²), and take only $T_{mod}=[20,30]^{\circ}C$ to see the effect of low irradiance on the efficiency. To avoid the weird behavior of the inverter for very low irradiation ($P_{ac}<100W$), we took only $G>150W/m^2$.

With linear regression $Y=p1X+p2$ in MATLAB, we can get ν_{fit} by putting:

$$\eta = \eta_{fit} + K_{p,fit} \eta_{fit} (T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \nu_{fit} \eta_{fit} \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right)$$

The linear fit:

$$\begin{cases} Y = \eta_{mes} = \frac{P_{ac,mes}}{S_u * N * G} \\ X = \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right) \\ p1 = \nu_{fit} \eta_{fit} \\ p2 = \eta_{fit} + K_{p,fit} \eta_{fit} (T_{mod} - T_{STC}) \end{cases} \quad Z = \nu_{fit} \eta_{fit} * \log \left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}} \right) + \left[\eta_{fit} + K_{p,fit} \eta_{fit} (T_{mod} - T_{STC}) \right]$$

The figure 31 below shows that the results obtained from the condition of fit 1:

Figure 31: The effect of irradiance on efficiency for polycrystalline(left) & amorphous(right)

As can be seen in figure 31, the efficiency is not really affected by irradiance ($G=[150-400 \text{ W/m}^2]$). Results reveals that for both technologies, the efficiency is very stable with the logarithm of G .

❖ **Conditions of fit 2- Filtering the high module temperature & high solar irradiance to get the coefficient of temperature $K_{p,fit}$:** $T_{mod} > 40^\circ\text{C}$; $G=[500,1100] \text{ W/m}^2$

After calculating the module temperature, we filter the high module temperature corresponding to $G=[500,1100] \text{ W/m}^2$ and $T_{mod} > 40^\circ\text{C}$ to see the effect of the high temperature on efficiency.

With linear regression $Y=p1X+p2$ in MATLAB, we can get $K_{p,fit}$ by putting:

$$\eta = \eta_{fit} + K_{p,fit} \eta_{fit} (T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \nu_{fit} \eta_{fit} \log\left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}}\right)$$

The linear fit: $Z = K_{p,fit} \eta_{fit} * (T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \left[\eta_{fit} + \nu_{fit} \eta_{fit} \log\left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}}\right) \right]$

$$\begin{cases} Y = \eta_{mes} = \frac{P_{dc,mes}}{S_u * N * G} \\ X = (T_{mod} - T_{STC}) \\ p1 = K_{p,fit} \eta_{fit} \\ p2 = \eta_{fit} + \nu_{fit} \eta_{fit} \log\left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}}\right) \end{cases}$$

The figure 32 below shows the results obtained from the condition of fit 2 :

Figure 32: The effect of high module temperature on efficiency for polycrystalline(left) & amorphous(right)

The efficiencies were compared with seasonally varying operating T_{mod} and irradiance. The efficiency of both a-Si and poly-Si modules are not shown for January 2011 to April 2011 due to insufficient data available for these months.

The efficiency of the **poly-Si** module shows a linear dependence on T_{mod} , that is, drops drastically with increasing T_{mod} . It reaches the minimum value in summer ($T_{mod} - T_{STC} = 45^\circ\text{C}$)

The opposite result is obtained for **the a-Si module**: The efficiency of the a-Si module increases gradually with increasing temperature T_{mod} due to the thermal-recovery effect. We can say that the efficiency for a-Si remains nearly unchanged from April to the end of June 2011 (corresponding to $T_{mod} - T_{STC} = 15 - 25^\circ\text{C}$), in which period the module temperature gradually increases. With approaching summertime, the a-Si modules starts to increase and reaches the highest value in August ($T_{mod} - T_{STC} = 25 - 45^\circ\text{C}$) in which operating temperature of the PV module becomes highest.

We can conclude that the a-Si module improves in summertime, whereas a better performance is observed in wintertime for the poly-Si module.

ii. Summary and validation of results: Comparison with Parameters of datasheets & literature

From the equations, taken from the graphs above, that calculate the slope p1 and the intercept p2 of each linear fit, we get the 3 unknown parameters fitted. These calculations and analysis are made under real operating conditions of the PV system installed in IUT Cachan over the first year of evaluation from April to December 2011.

The table 14 compares the regression results with the values in STC, specified in PV module's datasheet ($\eta_{STC}, K_{p,STC}$) and found in the literature (ν) [27][28]. These parameters are fitted using only the measurements of the year 2011 and will be fixed for the coming years.

In the case of working with datasheet parameters, the AC production simulated is expressed as:

$$P_{ac,sim} = \eta_{inv,STC} * \eta_{PV,STC} * \left[1 + K_{p,STC}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + \nu \log\left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}}\right) \right] * G * N_{mod,s} * S_u$$

The inverter efficiency at STC is 94.2 % (it's technical specification is presented in table 8 in chapter 3).

The parameter estimation results is presented in table 14:

Table14: Evans Model Parameter estimation & validation

	Fitted Coefficients (outdoor conditions)		Manufacturers' Datasheet ($\eta_{STC}, K_{p,STC}$) + literature (ν)	
	Poly	Amorphous	Poly	Amorphous
η_{fit}	0.1335	0.059	0.1369*0.942=0.1289 0.1369*0.97=0.1334	0.062*0.942=0.0584
$K_{p,fit}$ (/ K)	-3.65e-03	8.49e-04	-4.70e-03	-2e-03
γ_{fit}	1.85e-02	1.53e-03	0.12	0

The efficiency of the module is 13.69% for poly-Si and 6.2% for a-Si at STC measurements. As said before, the efficiency fitted η_{fit} take into account the efficiency of PV module and the efficiency of the inverter, that is assumed constant, because the linear regression was realized with measurements at AC side. **For Poly**, the efficiency of the inverter is assumed constant and we obtain 97.5% and **for amorphous** is assumed equal to the inverter efficiency at STC, 94.2%. Therefore, **the system (PV+Inverter)** should have an efficiency around 13.69%*97.5%=13.34% for poly-Si and around 6.2%*94.2%=5.84%. As demonstrate in table, we obtain an efficiency of 13.35% (~13.34%) for poly-Si and 5.9% (~5.84%) for amorphous-Si. Hence, the results agree with the STC measurements.

For **poly-Si**, Table 14 clearly show that the fitted power temperature coefficients $K_{p,fit}$ agree with the value provided by the manufacturer. We have almost the same result at STC and outdoor conditions. However, the value $K_{p,fit}$ of **a-Si** is the greatest. This leads to the higher lost of power of polycrystalline than amorphous when temperature increases.

For **poly-Si** (fig 32 left), the efficiency decreases when the T_{mod} increases. This is due to the fact that the coefficient of temperature of poly-Si is always negatif (at STC and at outdoor conditions). For **the amorphous** (fig 32 right), the efficiency increases as T_{mod} increases, due to the value of $K_{p,fit}$ that is found positif.

Plamen Tsankov [43] shows that **amorphous silicon** PV modules work 94 % of the time with relatively big positive power temperature coefficient, although their nominal power temperature coefficient at STC is negative whereas **polycrystalline** silicon PV modules work 62% of the time with negative power temperature coefficient, lower than the nominal at STC. It means that amorphous silicon PV modules work better than polycrystalline silicon PV modules in real operating conditions, and have minimum power loss with the elevation of PV module temperature.

These variations between the two cases (fitted coefficients and STC/literature parameters) can be explained by the fact that the parameters given by the manufacturer are not suited to the outdoor conditions (G, T_{mod}).

It is very remarkable that the determined coefficient of irradiance, for both technologies, are lower than the values found in the literature for **poly-Si** and higher than the value found for **amorphous**. It's normal because we filtered low irradiance for both conditions, (we took $G > 150W/m^2$ in the first condition of fit and $G = [500, 1100]W/m^2$).

It should be pointed out that these results with fitted coefficients are also similar (better in some cases) to the ones provided by the manufacturer or found in the literature.

Concluding remarks about the behavior of the power with G and Tmod:

To analyze the effect of G and T_{amb} , and see if Evans model agree with measurements, we plot the power simulated and measured as function of G and T_{mod} , using **the fitted coefficients** (figure33,34):

Figure33: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for poly-Si using fitted coefficients of Evans Model (outdoor conditions)

Figure34: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for amorphous using fitted coefficients of Evans Model (outdoor conditions)

It is observed, for **both technologies** that the measured power is very close to simulated one, as is clearly shown in Fig 33 for poly-si and (fig 34) for amorphous regardless of T_{amb} and G. The results confirm that the fit has been done successfully, which validate the Evans model.

The graphs of the simulated and measured power output with G and T_{amb} , for both technologies, for the other years of evaluation is presented in chapter 5.

d) Identification of the 3 unknown parameters of PVUSA Model

Model medelizing the AC power production of the PV system using solar irradiance and ambient temperature measurements was developed using hourly averaged data. Unlike the electrical model (SDM with 5 parameters), PVUSA model doesn't compute the I-V & P-V curves.

i. Fitted Coefficients Method

Turning to the detail, this model simulates the DC power, but as said in the chapter 2, and with the same assumption as we used with Evans Model, the corresponding parameters are found by filtering the data and applying linear/multiple regressions onto measurements in order to find the corresponding parameters.

As the power measured is provided at the AC side, hence the power of the module take into account the inverter efficiency η_{inv} which is assumed constant.

The AC production is expresses as [29]: $P_{ac,sim} = G(a_{fit} + b_{fit}G + c_{fit}T_{amb})$

$a_{fit}, b_{fit}, c_{fit}$ are coefficients fitted, so that the model result is as close as possible to the measured data.

This approach has been realised at outdoor conditions (G, T_{amb}) of the first year of evaluation (April to December 2011), and the values resulted will be fixed for the other years.

The extraction of the 3 unknown parameters require conditions of simulation in order to extract a reasonable value, which is discussed more in depth in the results section.

❖ Condition of fit 1-Filtering the constant values of ambient temperature:

$$T_{amb}=[20,30]^{\circ}\text{C}; G=[150,800] \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$$

Applying multiple regression $Y = p1X^2 + p2X + p3$ in MATLAB by putting: $P_{ac,sim} = G(a_{fit} + b_{fit}G + c_{fit}T_{amb})$

The linear fit: $Z = b_{fit}G^2 + [a_{fit} + c_{fit}Mean(T_{amb})]G + cst$

$$\begin{cases} X = G \\ Y = P_{ac,meas} \\ p1 = b_{fit} \\ p2 = a_{fit} + c_{fit} \cdot Mean(T_{amb}) \\ p3 = cst \approx 0 \end{cases}$$

Figure35: The effect of irradiance on AC power output for poly-Si (Left) & a-Si (right)

❖ **Condition of fit 2-Filtering the constant values of solar irradiance: $T_{amb} > 15^\circ\text{C}$; $G > 800 \text{ W/m}^2$**

Applying linear regression $Y=p1X+p2$ in MATLAB, by putting: $P_{ac,sim} = G(a_{fit} + b_{fit}G + c_{fit}T_{amb})$

The linear fit: $Z=c_{fit}G + [a_{fit}Mean(G) + b_{fit}Mean(G)^2]X + cst$

$$\begin{cases} X = T_{amb} \\ Y = P_{ac,meas} \\ p1 = c_{fit}G \\ p2 = (a_{fit}Mean(G) + b_{fit}Mean(G)^2) \end{cases}$$

Figure 36 : The effect of ambient temperature on AC power output for poly(left) & Amorphous (right)

In the **first condition of simulation** (fig35), the data perfectly fit a straight regression line. As can be seen in the figure, the solar irradiance and power production measurements follow a strong linear relationship, which confirm that the results obtained are accurate due to the better fitting curve for **both technologies**.

The results obtained however in the **second condition** (fig36) are different; it is clearly visible from the graph that the AC power of **poly-Si** is strongly dispersed with T_{amb} and shows a downward trend with rising T_{amb} (figure 36 left). This is due to the fact that the measurements in the second condition are taken only for constant values of irradiance ($G > 800 \text{ W/m}^2$), which means we don't have enough data (85 operating points). It leads to the result that the linear line is not perfect and therefore, it is very difficult to conclude that the slope of the linear line is the fit.

Similar result can be observed in the case of **amorphous**. Moreover, the figure36 right depicts that the production declines gradually with the T_{amb} ; while it increases gradually for amorphous when the T_{amb} goes up. It means that the higher temperature is, the less power production or the less efficiency obtain.

ii. Summary and validation of results: Comparison with Parameters of datasheets

The scatter graphs of production against irradiance and against T_{amb} (depending on which condition of simulation) are plotted in Figuree 35 and 36 and the slope of the fit provides the values of the 3 parameters. The results are shown in table 15 below.

Table15: PVUSA Model Parameter Estimation

PVUSA Model Fitted Parameters	Polycrystalline	Amorphous
a_{fit}	1.78	1.64
b_{fit}	-3.75e-04	-1.9e-04
c_{fit}	-5.8e-03	-3.47e-04

These parameters are fitted using only the measurements of the year 2011 and will be fixed for the coming years.

In order to check the accuracy of the values obtained. We turn back to Evans model [27][28]. The output power at AC side is expresses as:

$$P_{ac,sim} = \eta_{inv,STC} * \eta_{PV} * G * S_{tot}$$

Where, the efficiency of PV module in operating condition is expressed as [28]:

$$\eta_{PV} = \eta_{PV,STC} \left[1 + K_{p,STC}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) + v \log\left(\frac{G}{G_{STC}}\right) \right]$$

The PVUSA model neglects the coefficient of irradiance. Hence, the last term can be neglected [28]:

$$\eta_{PV} = \eta_{PV,STC} \left[1 + K_{p,STC}(T_{mod} - T_{STC}) \right]$$

By replacing the T_{mod} by its expression (Model NOCT) : $T_{mod} = T_{amb} + \frac{G}{800}(T_{NOCT} - 20)$

Thus, we get:

$$P_{ac,sim} = G \left[\eta_{inv,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} - \eta_{inv,STC} K_{p,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} T_{STC} + \eta_{inv,STC} K_{p,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} \left(\frac{T_{NOCT} - 20}{800} \right) G + \eta_{inv,STC} K_{p,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} T_{amb} \right]$$

If we put :

$$a_{STC} = \eta_{inv,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} - \eta_{inv,STC} K_{p,STC} \eta_{SPV,TC} S_{tot} T_{STC} = \eta_{inv,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} [1 - K_{p,STC} T_{STC}]$$

$$b_{STC} = \eta_{inv,STC} K_{p,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot} \left(\frac{T_{NOCT} - 20}{800} \right)$$

$$c_{STC} = \eta_{inv,STC} K_{p,STC} \eta_{PV,STC} S_{tot}$$

We obtain: $P_{ac,sim} = G[a_{STC} + b_{STC}G + c_{STC}T_{amb}]$ which is similar to the PVUSA Model.

To validate the fitted parameters of PVUSA Model, we compared these parameters at STC measurements with the values obtained with the regression technique. The calculated values of the 3 parameters in real working conditions and the nominal values calculated with parameters at STC are given in Table 16.

Table16: PVUSA Model Parameter Validation

PVUSA Model-Fitted Parameters	Polycrystalline	Amorphous	Relative Error between fitted & STC coefficients	
			Polycrystalline	Amorphous
a_{STC}	1.51	1.42	0,17	0,15
b_{STC}	-2.15e-04	-9.84e-05	-7,44e-01	-0,93
c_{STC}	-6.30e-03	-2.71e-03	-7,94e-02	-9,96e-01

When we looked into the fitted coefficients (table 15), we found that the coefficients are not far from each other (the RE is less than 1%), which leads to validate the values obtained.

Concluding remarks about the behavior of the power with G and Tmod:

To analyze the effect of G and T_{amb} , and to see if PVUSA model agree with measurements we plot the power simulated and measured as function of G and Tmod, using **the fitted coefficients**:

Figure37: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for poly-Si using fitted coefficients of PVUSA Model (outdoor conditions)

Figure38: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with a colorbar G (left) & T_{amb} (right) for amorphes using fitted coefficients of PVUSA Model (outdoor conditions)

As can be seen in figures 37 and 38, the PVUSA agree with measurements for both technologies regardless of G and T_{amb} , which confirm that the extraction of the parameters of PVUSA has been done successfully, which validate the empirical model (PVUSA).

The graphs of the simulated and-measured power output with G and T_{amb} , for both technologies, for the other years of evaluation is presented in chapter 5.

2. AC Power Output Simulation framework

The values of the unknown parameters of each model that were obtained from the conditions of simulation presented above are then used to simulate the production of each model. This production simulated will be compared to the measured power. The results are presented in next chapter.

Bearing in mind that with these parameters extracted, we get the output power modeled at AC side for Evans Model and PVUSA Model (Empirical Model), because the parameters were fitted using measurements at AC side. Hence, the inverter efficiency is considered constant for these 2 models. However, the Single-Diode-Model with 5 parameters (Electrical Model) simulates only the Maximum power point at DC Side. Hence, we need to modelize the inverter the efficiency to obtain the AC output power modeled by the SDM by solving non-linear curve-fitting equations.

The flowchat below outlines the general approach adopted:

Figure39: AC Power Output Simulation framework

And the inverter efficiency simulated is given as [49]: $\eta_{inv,sim} = y_0 + c_1[1 - \exp(-c_2 * P_{mpp,sim})]$
 y_0, c_1, c_2 can be determined using a non linear regression algorithm, such as the least square algorithm.

	Polycrystallins	Amorphes
y0	1	0.74
c1	0.05	-0.2
c2	0.2	0.2

The lsqcurvefit function needs as inputs the modeled production at DC side $P_{mpp,sim}$ and the measured inverter efficiency, which is expressed as: $\eta_{inv,meas} = \frac{P_{ac,meas}}{P_{mpp,sim}}$

The values obtained for both technologies are given in the table 17 below:

Table17: The inverter efficiency results

	η_{inv} Polycrystalline	η_{inv} Amorphous
2011	1.06	0.53

As can be seen in the equation above that simulate the inverter efficiency that the inverter efficiency depends on the simulated power output at DC side provided by SDM-5parameters model. With the same approach of Evans and PVUSA models, the inverter efficiency will be also simulated only for the first year of operation (2011) and fixed for the coming years. The difference is that in SDM-5parameters we have the simulated power at DC side because we don't make regression techniques to fit the model by using measurements at AC side, like Evans and PVUSA models. The value obtained will be used to simulate the AC power output of the electrical model (SDM-5 parameters) in each year of operation.

Chapter 5: Automatic fault diagnosis & Performance Monitoring in grid connected PV systems

Fault detection is important since PV installations have been shown to be susceptible to a wide range of fault conditions. Therefore when a PV module has a failure it has a big impact in the output power of the PV array. Moreover, although PV systems generally operate without problems, like our installation in IUT-Cachan, when faults or breakdowns do occur, these may not be detected for several months if no effective diagnosis and monitoring system are in place.

Therefore, this thesis section will review the performance of the grid connected PV systems (amorphous-Si modules and poly-Si modules) installed on the roof of IUT-Cachan, over the period of evaluation (from the year 2011 to 2016), by implementing fault diagnosis methods at AC and DC side.

The faults detection method at AC side is based on the comparison between the AC measured power and the modeled one (CMM) in order to analyse how many times the deviation of measurements from the expected values occur in the PV systems, we will include some statistics. Afterwards, we will implement two faults detection algorithms: one based on performance index and one based on power error.

The faults detection method at DC side is based on the Power losses analysis (PLA). Some algorithms for faults identification based on current & voltage errors and indicators are also proposed. The simulations of all the algorithms are considering a set of real measurements in healthy state (no faults present in the PV installation)

Then, we will test these faults diagnosis algorithms with measurements in faulty state by simulating short-circuited module in the installation. The thresholds and all the indicators will be explained and analyzed. The faulty state was studied for a-Si over the year 2016 and for poly over the year 2011, corresponding to the period when we have enough data and no synchronization trouble. Then, we have the impacts of faults on the behaviour of a PV system showing different results.

1. Faults Detection Method at AC side based on the Comparison between Measured and Modeled (CMM) generation output of a PV system

The purpose of this section is to compare the annual AC production of 3 models namely Single-Diode-Model (SDM) with 5 parameters (extracted), the Evans Model, and the empirical Model (PVUSA) against AC power measurements of the PV installation. Significant deviations is considered as faulty operation.

a) Statistical tools for comparison between measured and modeled production

The comparison between simulated and measured PV module power is evaluated by using statistical indicators explained in table 18. In this study, we have adopted the following indicators: RMSE, MAE, MBE, RMAE, RMBE, standard deviation, and R^2 . These statistics provided insight into the performance of the modeled data set relative to the measurements [17][44][45].

Table 18: Statistical tools

Indicator	Mathematical Expression
Root Mean Square Error/Deviation (RMSE/RMSD) (W)	$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_sim,i})^2}{N}}$ <p>MSE measures the average squared difference between the measured power and modeled one. It is always non-negative, and values closer to zero are better.</p> <p>RMSE indicates the absolute fit of the model to the data: how close the observed data points are to the model's predicted values. Lower values of RMSE indicate better fit.</p> $MAE \leq RMSE$ $R^2 < RMSE$ <p>RMSE in percentage is expressed as :</p> $RMSE = \frac{RMSE}{P_{ac_mes}} * 100$
Mean Absolute Error (MAE) in (W)	$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_sim,i} }{N}$ <p>It presents the average absolute difference between the measured power and the simulated one. MAE and RMSE are similar : both metrics can range from 0 to infinity and are indifferent to the direction of errors. Lower values are better</p>
Relative MAE (RMAE) in (%)	$RMAE = \frac{MAE}{P_{ac_mes}} * 100$
Mean Biases Error (MBE) in (W)	$MBE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_sim,i})}{N}$ <p>If the absolute value is not taken in MAE, the average error becomes MBE and it is usually intended to measure average model bias. It describes the direction (+/-) of the error or difference bias.</p>
Relative MBE (RMBE) in (%)	$RMBE = \frac{MBE}{P_{ac_mes}} * 100$
Determination Coefficient R^2 or "Nash-Sutcliffe model efficiency coefficient (NSE):	$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_sim,i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_mes,i})^2} = 1 - \frac{SSE}{SST} = 1 - \frac{N * MSE}{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_mes,i})^2}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o SSE: Error Sum of Square o SST: Total Sum of Square o SSR: Regression Sum of Square $R^2 = \begin{cases} 0; & SSE = SST: \text{the regression is a total failure} \\ \approx 1; & SSE = 0: \text{the model is perfect} \end{cases}$
Coefficient of residual mass (CRM) in (W)	$CRM = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N P_{ac_mes,i} - \sum_{i=1}^N P_{ac_sim,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^N P_{ac_mes,i}}$ $CRM = \begin{cases} 0: \text{Model is perfect} \\ < 0: \text{tendency to overestimate the measures} \\ > 0: \text{tendency to underestimate the measures} \end{cases}$
Standard deviation (W)	<p>The standard deviation of a random variable, data set is the square root of its variance.</p> $std_dev(\Delta P) = \sqrt{Var(\Delta P)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (\Delta P - \overline{\Delta P})^2}{N}} ; \Delta P = P_{ac_mes,i} - P_{ac_sim,i} \text{ is the power error (W);}$ $\overline{\Delta P} = \frac{\sum \Delta P}{N} \text{ is the average power error (W)}$ <p>It is used to quantify the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of data values. A low standard deviation indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean (the expected value) of the set, while a high standard deviation indicates that the data points are spread out over a wider range of values [50].</p>

b) Detection method at AC side based on power ratio & power comparison :

The flowchart below (Fig 40) presents the approach adopted:

Figure 40: Failure Detection Algorithm1 at AC side based on CMM approach

The analysis regards the 16 amorphous modules and the 8 polycrystallines modules for which a complete set of measurements were available, and takes into account all the recorded data, after the previous filtering process ($G < 200 \text{ W/m}^2$) for which the measurement accuracy is significantly reduced. Samples taken during the night are naturally ignored. However, the low irradiance filtering results in no sufficient data points especially in the years 2013, 2014, 2015 limit the usefulness of this step.

The comparison have been conducted between the historical AC power measurements and the simulated results of the 3 models developed, for all the years for amorphous and only 2011-2012-2013 for poly-Si, corresponding to the years when we don't have synchronization troubles. Then, the comparison is made for different seasons of the year 2012 (because in this year the two inverters had been operating for all the year.) to see how the deviation change with season. Then, different plots of the 2 powers with irradiance and ambient temperature have been conducted to validate the models.

To detect the faults at AC side, the normal operation limits were calculated using the ratio between the measured and modeled AC power to determine if it lies inside or outside the normal operation limits. Points outside the normal operation limits are considered faults. The performance index PR_{idx} "Output Power Ratio" is expressed as [39]: $PR_{idx} = \frac{P_{ac,meas}}{P_{ac,sim}}$.

The limits are calculated as [39] : Lower limit = $\mu - 3\sigma$; Upper limit = $\mu + 3\sigma$

Where μ and σ are the average and standard deviation, respectively, of the value of the ratio PR_{idx} over the training dataset (determined only for the first year of operation 2011 and will be fixed for the coming years). The results of the as well as mean values and standard deviations of the output power ratio as well as the lower limit and the upper limit of the first year of operation are shown in the table below :

Table 19: the boundaries fixed for the performance index

	Poly-Si 2011	Amorphous 2011
$\mu = Mean(PR_{idx})$	1.05	0.96
$\sigma = std_dev(PR_{idx})$	0.07	0.078
Lower limit = $\mu - 3\sigma$	0.83	0.72
Upper limit = $\mu + 3\sigma$	1.27	1.2

This ratio PR_{idx} is used to determine how close the measurements are to their expected values, according to the model : the closer this ratio is to 1, the closer the measured power is to the modeled value. The plus and minus 3 standard deviations ($\pm 3\sigma$) interval was chosen to calculate the normal operation limits [39].

The most straightforward way to rapidly gain first insights about the normal operation limits is to simply visualize the ratio PR_{idx} , the lower limit and the upper limit.

Finally, we are going to summarize the results with a series of graphics and tables that show for each year the deviations between the output powers.

i. Simulations and observations

The graphs demonstrate the bias differences between the measurements and the modeled AC power. The X-axis shows the time in which the measures take place for each year.

The main indicators which is used to evaluate the deviations from the measurements and the model such as MAE, MBE, RMAE, RMBE, R^2 and RMSE are visualized in the graphs. The evolution of the indicators have been calculated in each one of the models simulated.

While looking at the scatter graphs, we can observe that there are several low peaks corresponding to different moment in the period of study and the power measured and simulated have the same shape as irradiance which show the dependence of solar

irradiance on the season and its certain that PV modules converted more energy in sunny season (summer) than cloudy season (winter).

Graphical representations of the two productions with colorbar of the ambient temperature and irradiance are made separately for the three models and for the two technologies. Thus, we can observe easily the adequation between the models and data measurements.

❖ *Evans Model*

Indicators each year for Evans Model:

The figures below compare the measured and simulated power using Evans model as a function of time, and display the results of the statistical indicators.

Figure41: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ for poly-Si with Evans Model

Figure42 : $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ for Amorphous with Evans Model

When we observe at the production curve modeled of **amorphous** (fig 42) with Evans model, we observe that the modeled curve has the similar height and shape. However, we can observe there is some shift between 2 curves and the modeled curve is ahead of the measured curve (MBE and RMBE are negatives). However, for **poly** (fig 41) we can easily see that the simulated production is less than the measured one (MBE and RMBE are positives).

Table 20 : Statistical indicators results for each year using Evans Model

Indicators	Evans Model								
	Polycrystalline			Amorphous					
	Year 2011	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2011	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2014	Year 2015	Year 2016
Period of Simulation	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Dec	Sep-->Dec	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Dec	Sep-->Dec	Jan-->Mar	Oct-->Dec	Jan-->Sep
MAE (W)	42.37	42.37	46.86	27.66	24.90	47.92	56.43	85.25	39.59
MBE (W)	34.57	34.57	34.24	-14.72	-12.34	-39.13	-56.43	-85.25	-39.44
RMAE (%)	6.63	6.63	8.49	4.22	3.74	9.33	12.62	19.67	6.26
RMBE (%)	5.41	5.41	6.20	-2.24	-1.85	-7.63	-12.62	-19.67	-6.23
R ²	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.97	0.98	0.91	0.90	0.69	0.97
RMSE (W)	53.93	53.93	55.49	47.50	36.94	64.65	60.89	90.38	47.63
RMSE (%)	8.44	8.44	10.06	7.24	5.55	12.59	13.62	20.85	7.53
N	1147	1147	231	1195	1606	310	132	165	1360

As mentioned above from the results obtained from the statistical indicators; although the production fluctuates a lot the deviation **for poly** the deviation is quite small all the years (RMAE=6-8.5%). For **amorphous**, the deviations (RMAE, MAE,

RMSE) are quite small in 2011-2012-2016 (RMAE around 4% and 6% in 2016) compared to 2013-2014-2015 (RMAE around 9% and reach the highest value in 2015). The highest deviations are for 2014-2015 (RMAE=12-19%).

Indicators each season for Evans Model

Since the yearly graphics doesn't have any information of the reasons of the deviation. We will study the statistics for different seasons. Let's now analyse the 4 seasons of the year 2012.

Figure 43: $P_{ac, sim} = f(P_{ac, meas})$ for different seasons of 2012-Poly (left) Amorphous (Right) with Evans Model

Figure 44: RMAE (%) as function of seasons with Evans Model

Table 21: Statistical indicators results for each seasons using Evans Model

Indicators	Evans Model							
	Polycrystalline 2012				Amorphous 2012			
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn
MAE (W)	181.09	37.63	52.76	76.18	83.10	15.92	18.61	104.04
MBE (W)	103.34	37.63	49.49	25.82	-83.10	5	0.25	-104.04
RMAE (%)	25.04	6.57	7.33	14.75	14.83	2.66	2.44	27.02
RMBE (%)	14.29	6.57	6.87	5	-14.83	0.83	0.033	-27.02
R^2	-1.23	0.96	0.94	0.74	0.68	0.99	0.99	0.36
RMSE (W)	122.49	39.66	57.57	94.06	111.8	20.11	23.14	110.68
RMSE (%)	30.77	6.92	7.99	18.22	19.69	3.36	3.03	28.74
N	5	44	132	21	41	106	132	24

As we can see in fig 43 the production simulated by Evans model contain lots of deviation, especially at cold periods for **both technologies** because of the low temperature and irradiance in this periods. We have a lot of deviations (MAE, RMAE, RMSE) in autumn and winter and quite small deviations in spring and summer, especially for amorphous. The RMAE is around 7% for poly-si and only 2.5% for amorphous in spring and winter.

As can be seen in figure 15, the deviation is more pronounced in winter for poly; and more in autumn for amorphous.

These results confirm what it stated in the section of identification of Evans parameters. The coefficient of temperature is always negativ for poly and positif for amorphous at outdoor conditions in spite of its lowest efficiency it works well in sunny conditions, which means that there is loss of production for poly-Si when G and T_{amb} increase compared to amorphous.

Deviations with G & T_{amb} for Evans Model:

Figure 45: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with irradiance(left) & ambient temperature (right) for Poly-Si with Evans Model

Figure46: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with irradiance for Amorphous with Evans Model

Figure47: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with ambient temperature for Amorphous with Evans Model

As can be seen in figure 43 for poly-Si and figures 45 and 46 for amorphous that Evans model agree with measurements all the years and regardless of G and T_{amb} which confirm that the identification parameters results of Evans model is accurate and validate the model.

Normal Operation Limits for Evans Model:

The ratio between the measured production and the modeled one is found to be around 1 (fig 48 for poly and fig 49 for amorphous), and all the years between the lower and the upper limits, which agree with the thresholds of normal operation

limits. Therefore, the algorithm emits the alarm “normal operation” all the years (table 27). However, we can see easily that sometimes the power ration either exceeds the lower limits or exceeds the upper limits, especially in the beginning and the end of each year.

Figure 48: Normal Operation Limits for Poly-Si with Evans Model

Figure 49: Normal Operation Limits for Amorphous with Evans Model

❖ Empirical Model (PVUSA)

Indicators each year for PVUSA Model:

The yearly results of the indicators that calculate the deviation between the measured and simulated power using PVUSA model for both technologies can be seen in the graphs 50 and 51:

We can easily see that the production curve modeled, by PVUSA model, of the two technologies, is ahead of the measured curve (MBE and RMBE are negatives).

Figure 50: $P_{ac,sim} = f(P_{ac,meas})$ for poly-Si with PVUSA Model

Figure 51: $P_{ac, sim} = f(P_{ac, meas})$ for Amorphous with PVUSA Model

Table 22: Statistical indicators results for each year using PVUSA Model

Indicators	Empirical Model								
	Polycrystalline			Amorphous					
	Year 2011	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2011	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2014	Year 2015	Year 2016
Period of Simulation	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Dec	Sep-->Dec	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Dec	Sep-->Dec	Jan-->Mar	Oct-->Dec	Jan-->Sep
MAE (W)	50.67	42.66	51.64	81.20	79.33	108.48	125.25	155.09	104.87
MBE (W)	-49.79	-41.15	-47.58	-81.16	-79.33	-108.48	-125.25	-155.09	-104.87
RMAE (%)	7.93	6.56	9.36	12.39	11.91	21.13	28.03	35.78	16.58
RMBE (%)	-7.79	-6.33	-8.62	-12.38	-11.91	-21.13	-28.03	-35.78	-16.58
R^2	0.93	0.95	0.91	0.89	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.036	0.85
RMSE (W)	62.9	52.13	62.63	93.57	87.88	121.56	128.09	159.46	109.5
RMSE (%)	9.84	8.02	11.35	14.28	13.20	23.68	28.66	36.79	17.31
N	1147	1011	231	1195	1606	310	132	165	1360

As demonstrate in the table 22 above, **for poly** the deviations (MAE, RMAE, RMSE) are quite small for poly (RMAE=6-9%). For **amorphous**, the deviations (RMAE, MAE, RMSE) are quite small in 2011-2012-2016 (RMAE around 12% and 17% in 2016) compared to 2013-2014-2015 (RMAE around 21-36%). The highest deviations are for 2014-2015 (RMAE=28-36%). We have similar results with Evans model but the deviations are quite higher with PVUSA model than Evans model.

Indicators each season for PVUSA Model:

The year 2012 represent 4 seasons were chosen as an example for the seasonal analysis.

Figure 52: $P_{ac, sim} = f(P_{ac, meas})$ for different seasons of 2012-Poly (left) Amorphous (right) with PVUSA Model

Figure 53: RMAE (%) as a function of seasons with PVUSA Model

Table 23 : Statistical indicators results for each seasons using PVUSA Model

Indicators	Empirical Model							
	Polycrystalline 2012				Amorphous 2012			
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn
MAE (W)	162.25	45.64	36.56	59.36	157.09	61.32	63.03	177.4
MBE (W)	30.21	-45.64	-35.31	-58.66	-157.09	-61.32	-63.03	-177.4
RMAE (%)	22.41	7.96	5.07	11.49	28.05	10.25	8.27	46.07
RMBE (%)	4.17	-7.96	-4.9	-11.36	-28.05	-10.25	-8.27	-46.07
R ²	-0.88	0.94	0.96	0.68	0.13	0.94	0.94	0.72
RMSE (W)	204.58	46.32	43.67	104.46	184.24	63.23	66.97	182.10
RMSE (%)	28.29	8.08	6.068	20.23	32.89	10.5	8.78	47.29
N	5	44	132	24	41	106	132	24

As can be seen that the deviation in spring and summer is less than the deviation in winter and autumn for both technologies. The results of the comparison are shown in table 23 and are similar with what we found with Evans Model. However, the errors are quite higher than what we found with Evans Model (RMAE is around 8% for poly and around 10% for amorphous) in spring and winter. Another thing worth to note is with PVUSA, we have more deviation for amorphous than poly-Si, not similar with what we found with Evans.

Deviations with G & T_{amb} for PVUSA Model:

The air temperature follows the same trend as irradiance. For **amorphous** (figs 55-56) show that the power data stays always in the straight line. For **poly** (fig 54) the two powers has a strong linear relationship regardless of G and T_{amb} . Therefore, the parameters extraction of PVUSA has been done successfully.

Figure 54: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with irradiance (left) & ambient temperature (right) for Poly-Si with PVUSA Model

Figure55: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with Solar irradiance for Amorphous with PVUSA Model

Figure56 : $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with ambient temperature for Amorphous with PVUSA Model

Normal Operation Limits for PVUSA Model:

As can be seen in the figures 57-58, for **poly**, and **amorphous**, the data is inside the normal operation limits all the years except some periods corresponding to the beginning and the end of each year. The algorithm results « normal operation» all the years for both technologies (table 28). But, the performance index is sometimes less than the lower limit and sometimes higher than the upper limit all the year, which not agree with the thresholds of normal operation limits all the time.

Figure 57: Normal Operation Limits for Poly-Si with PVUSA Model

Figure58: Normal Operation Limits for Amorphous with PVUSA Model

❖ Single-Diode-5parameters Model

Indicators each year for SDM-5parameters Model:

The yearly results of the indicators for both technologies can be seen in the graphs 59 and 60 :

Figure 59: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ for poly-Si with SDM-parameters Model

Figure 60: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ for Amorphous-Si with SDM-parameters Model

As can be seen in the graphs above, for **poly**, it could be easily to see that the modeled power match the measured one and less deviations are observed. The max value of RMAE for **poly-Si** is around 8%. The gap and shift are much narrowed as compared with Amorphous-Si.

For **amorphous**, the plots show that the modeled production curve is close to the measured curve but we have some deviations. The MAE is around 32-49%.

Table 24: Statistical indicators results for each year using SDM Model

Indicators	SDM-5 parameters extracted								
	Polycrystalline			Amorphous					
	Year 2011	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2011	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2014	Year 2015	Year 2016
Period of Simulation	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Dec	Sep-->Dec	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Dec	Sep-->Dec	Jan-->Mar	Oct-->Dec	Jan-->Sep
MAE (W)	20.01	18.59	27.47	40.91	43.99	48.46	39.87	65.99	31.59
MBE (W)	-3.06	8.16	8.45	10.74	25.14	-13.78	-34.94	-64.7	-4.4
RMAE (%)	3.13	2.86	4.98	6.24	6.61	9.44	8.92	15.22	4.99
RMBE (%)	-0.48	1.25	1.53	1.63	3.77	-2.68	-7.82	-14.93	-0.69
R ²	0.97	0.98	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.92	0.94	0.79	0.97
RMSE (W)	39.11	30.11	40.93	56.4	55.35	62.31	47.26	73.38	40.36
RMSE (%)	6.12	4.63	7.42	8.6	8.31	12.14	10.57	16.93	6.38
N	1147	1011	231	1195	1606	310	132	165	1360

With SDM-5parameters model, we have small deviations for poly (The max value of RMAE is 5%). For **amorphous**, the deviations are quite small in 2011-2012-2016 (RMAE around 5-6%) compared to 2013-2014-2015 (RMAE around 9%). The highest deviations are for 2015 (RMAE=15.22%).

The results are similar to the analysis results of PVUSA Model; we have always less deviation in poly-Si than amorphous.

Indicators each season for SDM-5 parameters Model

The seasonal results of the indicators for both technologies can be seen in the graph 61 :

Figure 61 : $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ for different seasons of 2012 for Poly (left) & Amorphous (right) with SDM-5 parameters Model

Figure62: RMAE as a function of seasons with SDM-5parameters model

Table 25: Statistical indicators results for each season using SDM Model

Indicators	SDM-5 parameters extracted							
	Polycrystalline 2012				Amorphous 2012			
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn
MAE (W)	172.79	15.40	15.13	5.53	528.86	523.09	687.54	516.50
MBE (W)	72.04	10.45	7.29	0.87	-528.86	-523.09	-687.54	-516.50
RMAE (%)	23.89	2.68	2.10	10.75	94.43	87.47	90.23	134.14
RMBE (%)	9.96	1.82	1.01	0.16	-94.43	-87.47	-90.23	-134.14
R ²	-1.20	0.99	0.99	0.78	-9.66	-3.49	-5.14	-15.13

RMSE (W)	221.02	17.50	20.37	85.29	646.75	554.65	737.41	556.13
RMSE (%)	30.56	3.05	2.83	16.52	115.48	92.75	96.77	144.43
N	5	44	132	24	41	106	132	24

It can be seen clearly that the modules have different seasonal behavior. If we look at the table 25 above, we can see right away that the **Poly-Si** has small deviation (around 2.7%) at high irradiance and Tamb, which correspond to **spring and summer**. A very good consistency can be seen between the measured curves and the simulated ones (figure 61). We have also less deviations in spring and summer for **amorphous**, as compared to winter and autumn, but the values of RMAE, MAE, RMSE are very high. This is due to the fact that parameters extraction of SDM_5parameters of amorphous has not been done accurately. The result one more time confirms that the extraction of the electrical model for amorphous hasn't been done successfully. However, this not convenient for us to make further comparisons.

The results are similar to the analysis results of Evans and PVUSA Model , we have always less deviation in spring and summer and more deviations in winter and autumn. In Evans, we have less deviation for amorphous compared to poly-si in spring and summer. However, for PVUSA and SDM-5parameters, we have more deviations with amorphous than poly-Si.

Another thing is that the highest deviation correspond to winter for poly and autumn for amorphous.

Deviations with G & Tamb for SDM-5 parameters Model:

Figure 63: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with irradiance (left) & ambient temperature (right) for Poly-Si with SDM-5 parameters Model

Figure 64: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with irradiance for Amorphous-Si with SDM-5 parameters Model

Figure 65: $P_{ac,sim}=f(P_{ac,meas})$ with ambient temperature for Amorphous-Si with SDM-5 parameters Model

Additionally, looking to the graphs above (figs63 to 65), the result also indicates there is a small difference between the graph of amorphous and poly. For amorphous we have data quite dispersed above and below the straight line, this is only due to the parameters of SDM of amorphous. Overall, there is a good agreement between simulation results and monitored data over the period of evaluation, which validates the electrical model for the two technologies.

Normal Operation Limits for SDM-5 parameters Model:

As you can see from the plots 66-67, for poly and amorphous, the ratio is between the lower and the upper limits all the years except some periods corresponding to the beginning and the end of each year, for both technologies. The algorithm also emit an alarm of “normal operation” all the years (table 26).

The results of SDM-5parameters is similar with what we found with Evans and PVUSA models.

Figure 66: Normal Operation Limits for Poly-Si with SDM-5 parameters Model

Figure 67 : Normal Operation Limits for Amorphous-Si with SDM-5 parameters Model

ii. Summary and validation of the results

In this section we presented a general approach to compare measured and simulated data of a PV installation using 3 models. The aim of this method is to validate the models, detect possible problems in the simulation parameters and get an overview of the system performance. Overall, there is a good agreement between simulation results and monitored data over the period of evaluation.

As said before, we didn't take into account the period with low sun ($G < 200 \text{ W/m}^2$), these periods corresponds to the periods when the unstable operation occurred and so this situation is not related to any fault and we cannot draw conclusions about it when only looking at these periods.

The results show for Evans model the deviation **for poly** the deviation is quite small for poly (RMAE=6-8.5%). For **amorphous**, the deviations (RMAE, MAE, RMSE) are quite small in 2011-2012-2016 (RMAE around 4% and 6% in 2016) compared to 2013-2014-2015 (RMAE around 9% and reach the highest value in 2015). The highest deviations are for 2014-2015 (RMAE=12-19%).

For PVUSA model, it has been observed that the deviations are quite small for poly (RMAE=6-9%). For **amorphous**, the deviations are quite small in 2011-2012-2016 (RMAE around 12% and 17% in 2016) compared to 2013-2014-2015 (RMAE around 21-36%). The highest deviations are for 2014-2015 (RMAE=28-36%).

For SDM-5parameters model, we have small deviations **for poly** (The max value of RMAE is 5%). For **amorphous**, the deviations are quite small in 2011-2012-2016 (RMAE around 5-6%) compared to 2013-2014-2015 (RMAE around 9%). The highest deviations are for 2015 (RMAE=15.22%).

Therefore, for poly-si, we have small deviations with SDM-5 parameters model; and for amorphous, less deviations is found with Evans Model. The highest deviations are found with PVUSA model for both technologies. We can say that the parameters extraction has been done successfully for poly using SDM and for amorphous using Evans model because the statistical errors are small for the 3 models. For amorphous, we have quite high deviations especially in 2014-2015. It doesn't allow, however, drawing conclusions that there is faulty functioning, which is something we'll cover later in the next algorithms (based on power error).

As said before, this section detects the faults at the AC side. The plots of the ratio between the AC power measured and the AC power simulated versus time were done to check if the ratio "Performance index" does not exceed the defined thresholds over the period of evaluation (year by year). The thresholds help us to decide whether to trigger the alarm or not. The flowchart that explain the procedure of the failure detection at AC side using the power ratio is shown in figure 40 above, and the results of normal operation is presented in tables 26-27 and 28. The algorithm emit "normal operation" all the years for both technologies and all the 3 models, but it is clear in the graphs of normal operation limits that some periods of time corresponding to the beginning and the end of each year, the power ratio don't lie inside the thresholds established.

To validate however this approach of faults detection, we use another algorithm to confirm the normal operation of the PV installation of IUT Cachan. And to explain the high deviations found for amorphous in 2013-2014-2015.

c) Detection Algorithm at AC side based on power error:

This algorithm is based on power error: $\Delta P = |P_{ac,meas} - P_{ac,sim}|$

In order to avoid an excessive number of false faults detection, it is necessary to establish a specific threshold for ΔP to indicate proper operation of the system. For this purpose, we established thresholds for this parameter Th_p . If the value does not exceed defined thresholds, then it is considered that the PV system is working fault free, otherwise the PV system is considered in faulty operation. It helps us to decide whether to trigger the alarm or not.

The thresholds are calculated according to the maximum error introduced by the measurement noise and the model uncertainty:

- We consider that the sensors used to test the proposed diagnostic system are supposed within the specifications required by the IEC 61724 standard [46] indicating a relative error of 1%, 1%, and 2% for current, voltage, and power measurement, respectively.

- The model uncertainty is related to sensor noise and the manufacturing tolerance. According to [47], the maximum error introduced by this uncertainty is calculated by adding a dispersion parameter to the simulation model parameters. The obtained relative errors associated with current, voltage, and power is equal to 3.0%, 2.9%, and 5.9%, ly. Thresholds (Th_p , Th_c and Th_v) are obtained by adding errors introduced by both model and measurement uncertainties:

$$Th_c = I_{sc,STC}(1\% + 3\%) ; \quad Th_v = V_{mpp,STC}(1\% + 2.9\%) ; \quad Th_p = P_{mpp,STC}(2\% + 5.9\%)$$

Let's focus now only on the threshold of power. The thresholds of current and voltage (Th_p , Th_c) will be used later in the algorithms of faults identification at the DC side.

The flowchart below explains the procedure of the failure detection at AC side using the error power:

Figure 68: Fault Detection Algorithm 2 at AC side based on the power error

The threshold is calculated only for 2011 and will be fixed for the coming years :

Polycrystallines	Amorphous
$Th_p = 113.56W$	$Th_p = 113.92W$

❖ Results of Single diode model :

❖ Results of Evans Model :

❖ **Results of PVUSA Model :**

d) Results of the two detection algorithms at AC side :

The tables below present the results of the two Faults detection algorithms proposed at AC side to confirm the normal operation of the PV installation. We are going to present the results before analyzing and discussing them.

Table 26: Results of faults detection algorithms at AC side using SDM-5parameters Model

	SDM-5 parameters extracted			
	Polycrystalline		Amorphous	
	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)
2011	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2012	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2013	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2014	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2015	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2016	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation

Table27: Results of faults detection algorithms at AC side using Evans Model

	Evans Model			
	Polycrystalline		Amorphous	
	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)
2011	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2012	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2013	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2014	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2015	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2016	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation

Table 28 : Results of faults detection algorithms at AC side using PVUSA Model

	PVUSA Model			
	Polycrystalline		Amorphous	
	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)
2011	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2012	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2013	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2014	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2015	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation
2016	-	-	Faulty operation	Faulty operation

For **both technologies**, the performance index PR_{idx} (**algorithm 1**) and the parameter ΔP (**Algorithm 2**) don't remain within the established thresholds at all the years, using **the 3 models** so no alert signals are generated.

Despite having a certainty that all the equipment was installed carefully, but the deterioration of data can occur during the measurement process. Moreover, when disturbances in the grid induce inverter disconnections, deviations between simulated and monitored power are observed, and hence the algorithm based on power deviation generate faulty operation. So, a grid failure is then identified.

2. Fault Diagnosis Method at DC side based on the Power Loss Analysis (PLA) and Current & Voltage errors & indicators

In the previous section, the investigation was focused on the deviations and malfunctions at AC side. In this section, we will focus on the DC side because until now there is no common way to prevent excessive losses or components breakdown at this part of the PV system contrary to the AC side where the inverters are well protected against improperly functions.

a) Global approach of failure diagnosis based on PLA

Failure diagnosis is about detecting, identifying fast degradation occurring in solar panels and emitting alerts when we are losing too much power over a certain time period or when we're losing more money than what a maintenance intervention would cost. Developing practical fault diagnosis methods that has a relatively low degree of complexity, is able to deal with erroneous measurements and abnormal values, and achieves a high level of accuracy was the main requirement of this study. Therefore the method we propose in this study does not require knowledge of advanced methods, like artificial intelligence techniques. It involves both analyses of power losses, current and voltage, and the different effects being observed, as discussed in the literature study (chapter 2). This diagnostic procedure is able to detect and identify the most likely causes of the major failures of PV systems in real time.

There will be different algorithms: **“The power loss”** algorithm that detect if there is a fault in the system; and it is based on the measured and the simulated capture losses L_c . Three other algorithms that identify the type of the faults that may be occurred in the installation: Algorithm 1 and 2 are based on the difference between the measured and the simulated current ΔI and voltage ΔV at the DC side **“The CMM of Current & Voltage”**. Algorithm 3 is based on the current and voltage indicators (R_c, R_v). Changes in these patterns may represent faults or unwanted behavior within the components of the system.

This approach was developed using historical measurements from 90W-amorphous modules and 180W polycrystallines modules located in the roof of IUT Cachan. The fault detection algorithm was validated with data that include measurements that refer to the actual free fault operation of the PV system using hourly averaged data.

All the steps of failure diagnosis included in the algorithms will be analyzed and explained in the following sections on this chapter.

i. Fault detection Algorithm at DC side based on capture losses:

The power loss indicators used for this fault detection are are well explained in chapter 2. For this reason, we're just going to make brief mention to the indicators used. The capture losses are the losses that occur mainly at the DC side of the PV system. It's the sum of the thermal losses L_{ct} and the miscellaneous capture losses L_{cm} : The thermal losses are due to the decrease of the DC power when the PV modules are working at temperature higher than reference temperature (25°C). The miscellaneous losses are mainly due to faulty operation (faulty strings; short circuited modules, partial shadowing, low irradiance losses..).

The capture losses are expresses as [32]: $L_c = L_{ct} + L_{cm} = Y_r(G, T_{mod}) - Y_a(G, T_{mod})$ Where $Y_r = \frac{\sum_1^N G_{st}}{G_{STC}}$ is the reference yield and $Y_a = \frac{\sum_1^N P_{dc} \cdot t}{P_{mpp,STC} \cdot N_{mod}}$ is the array yield with N is the number of observations (operation working point in each year) and t is the monitoring time interval (t=1h because the simulations are done only using only hourly average data instead of 15-min measurements).

Once the capture losses are calculated from measurements and models, we set and apply thresholds that have to detect for a certain time period if the system is in its normal operation or no. In this section, it should confirm a fault-free operation of the system, since we didn't inject the faults yet.

The flowchart below (Fig 69) explains the process of faults detection using capture losses:

Figure 69: Faults detection Algorithm at AC side using Capture losses

Where $\sigma(L_{c,sim})$ is the standard deviation, calculated in yearly basis of simulated capture losses only in the first year of operation 2011 and will be fixed for the coming years. And for each year we will evaluate if $L_{c,meas}$ lies inside the thresholds established in 2011. The results of the thresholds of the first year of operation are shown in the table below :

Table 29: The standard deviation of the capture losses parameter in 2011

	Poly-Si 2011	Amorphous 2011
$\sigma = std_dev(L_{c,sim})$	0	0
$L_{c,sim} - 2\sigma(L_{c,sim})$	-69.68	-414.24
$L_{c,sim} + 2\sigma(L_{c,sim})$	69.68	414.24

The simulation of the fault detection method will be implemented using the only SDM with 5 parameters model because it simulate directly the power at the DC side. We use the inverter efficiency to convert the AC power measured to the DC power measured.

The process of calculating the capture losses for the SDM model is done by following steps:

$$L_{c,meas} = \frac{\sum_{year} G * t}{G_{STC}} - \frac{\sum_{year} P_{ac,meas} / \eta_{inv,sim} * t}{P_{mpp,STC} * N_{mod}} ; \quad L_{c,sim} = \frac{\sum_{year} G * t}{G_{STC}} - \frac{\sum_{year} P_{mpp,sim} * t}{P_{mpp,STC} * N_{mod}}$$

The main idea of this method of system diagnosis and fault detection was based on the continuous check of the DC measured capture losses. For this purpose, were established theoretical boundaries in which the measured capture losses do not exceed any of them, otherwise the system is considered in faulty operation [37][38][80].

When the $L_{c,meas}$ parameter exceeds the limit set, indicating the presence of a fault in the PV system is necessary to determine the most probable cause of this fault (start the identification algorithm).

We implemented this algorithm also to the free fault data and we obtain “ faulty operation”. Let’s now identify the problem.

ii. Fault Identification Algorithm 1 at DC side based on current & voltage:

Once we detect the presence of faults by the detection algorithm, we have to precisely identify which fault has occurred. The indicators that have been used to **identify the faults** are the current and the voltage. A set of boundaries has been defined for the current and voltage following the same procedure used above for $L_{c,meas}$. Then, we program the algorithm to warn us whenever the measured voltage or current drops below the threshold.

It’s important to note that we only have the DC measured voltage $V_{dc,meas}$, we don’t have the measures of the current and the power at the DC side. So we will use the inverter efficiency that was modeled for each year and each technology. The DC current estimated is then expresses as: $I_{dc,meas} = \frac{P_{ac,meas} / \eta_{inv,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}}$

Therefore, the algorithm of identification of faults is only available for SDM, because it’s the only one that provide the simulated current $I_{mpp,sim}$ and voltage $V_{mpp,sim}$ at the DC side.

The flowchart below (Fig 70) explains the process of faults identification using the voltage and current errors:

Figure 70: Fault Identification Algorithm1 at DC side using voltage and current errors

Where $\sigma(I_{mpp,sim})$ and $\sigma(V_{mpp,sim})$ are the standard deviation, calculated in yearly basis of simulated DC current and voltage of the first year of operation 2011. The results are shown in the table below :

Table 30: The standard deviation of the current & voltage in 2011

	Polycrystallines 2011	Amorphous 2011
$2\sigma(I_{mpp,sim})$	$2 * 0.94 = 1.88 \text{ A}$	$2 * 1.44 = 2.88 \text{ A}$
$\sigma(V_{mpp,sim})$	$2 * 0.83 = 1.66 \text{ V}$	$2 * 0.84 = 1.68 \text{ V}$

Unlike $L_{c,sim}$ we can display the results of the boundaries established for the measured current $I_{dc,meas}$ and the measured voltage $V_{dc,meas}$: $I_{mpp,sim} - 2\sigma(I_{mpp,sim}) ; I_{mpp,sim} + 2\sigma(I_{mpp,sim}) ; V_{mpp,sim} - 2\sigma(V_{mpp,sim}) ; V_{mpp,sim} + 2\sigma(V_{mpp,sim})$ because these boundaries changes with operating conditions (G, T_{mod}) of each year. Hence it’s not one value. But these boundaries can’t be calculated only for 2011 and fixed for the coming years since the data points are not the same in all the year (the parameters don’t have the same length). Therefore, we will fix $\sigma(I_{mpp,sim})$ and $\sigma(V_{mpp,sim})$ calculated for 2011 for each year we will evaluate if $I_{dc,meas}$ and $V_{dc,meas}$ remain inside the thresholds established in 2011 by evaluating also $I_{mpp,sim}$ and $V_{mpp,sim}$ for each year.

iii. Fault Identification Algorithm 2 at DC side based on current & voltage errors:

Another algorithm is proposed to find out the most probable faults present in the system when the $L_{c,meas}$ parameter exceeds the limits.

The thresholds of the current and voltage are already explained in the previous section [46][47]. We have identified that the PV system works in fault free operation when the errors ΔV and ΔI are below the thresholds. This algorithm was used only for SDM because it's the only one that gives us the current and voltage simulated. And the measured DC current is expressed following the

$$I_{dc,meas} = \frac{P_{ac,meas} / \eta_{inv,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}}$$

Fig 71 shows a flowchart of the proposed algorithm to find out the most likely faults, which have caused the losses detected in the PV systems.

Figure 71: Fault Identification Algorithm 2 at DC side using voltage and current errors

The thresholds are fixed only for 2011 and will be fixed for the coming years :

Polycristallines	Amorphous
$Th_c = 0.21 A$	$Th_c = 0.26 A$
$Th_v = 13.91 V$	$Th_v = 14.6 V$

iv. Fault Identification Algorithm 3 at DC side based on current & voltage indicators:

Another approach to determine the failure type is to define two indicators: the current and voltage ratios given by the following expressions [48]:

$$R_c = \frac{I_{dc,sim}}{I_{dc,meas}} = \frac{I_{mpp,sim}}{\frac{P_{ac,meas}}{V_{dc,meas}}} = \frac{I_{mpp,sim}}{\frac{P_{ac,meas} / \eta_{inv,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}}} ; \quad R_v = \frac{V_{dc,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}} = \frac{V_{mpp,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}}$$

Where $I_{dc,meas}$, $V_{dc,meas}$ are the current and voltage measured at the DC output of the PV array respectively, $P_{ac,meas}$ is the power measured at the AC output of the system and $I_{mpp,sim}$, $\eta_{inv,sim}$ are the DC current and the inverter efficiency simulated.

We should keep in mind that the failure identification used only the Electrical Model (SDM-5parameters model previously developed) because it's the only one that provide the simulation of the current and the voltage at the DC side.

R_c and $R_v > 1$ means ΔI and $\Delta V < 0$.

Analysing the ratios, the most probable failure or malfunction is found following the flowchart at Figure 72 below [48]:

Figure 72: Fault Identification Algorithm3 at DC side using current & voltage indicators

The basic idea of these faults identification algorithms is that we see when there is a problem in current & voltage and if the problem remains we see which faults exhibit a significant drop in the output voltage or the output current.

b) Results of the Faults Detection & Identification algorithms at DC side

This section describes the results retrieved using the proposed faults detection & Identification algorithms at DC side.

It's important to note that the fault identification algorithms are used to identify which problem occurs; hence they are implemented only if the faults detection algorithms emit an alarm of "faulty operation". However, we aim to test these proposed algorithms to our data that's why even the faults detection algorithm emit an alarm of "normal operation" we verify with faults detection algorithms if its false alarm (which means no problem) or no.

Table31: Results of faults detection & identification algorithms at DC side using SDM-5 parameters

	Modèle SDM-5 paramètres					
	Polycristallines			Amorphous		
	Algorithm 1	Algorithm 2	Algorithm 3	Algorithm 1	Algorithm 2	Algorithm 3
2011	$\Delta I > 1.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.66V$	$\Delta I > 0.21A$ $\Delta V > 13.91V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$	$\Delta I > 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.68V$	$\Delta I > 0.26A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$
2012	$\Delta I > 1.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.66V$	$\Delta I > 0.21A$ $\Delta V > 13.91V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$	$\Delta I < 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.68V$	$\Delta I > 0.26A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$
2013	$\Delta I < 1.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.66V$	$\Delta I > 0.21A$ $\Delta V > 13.91V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$	$\Delta I < 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.68V$	$\Delta I > 0.26A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$
2014	-	-	-	$\Delta I < 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.68V$	$\Delta I > 0.26A$ $\Delta V > 14.61V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$
2015	-	-	-	$\Delta I < 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.68V$	$\Delta I > 0.26A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$
2016	-	-	-	$\Delta I < 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 1.68V$	$\Delta I > 0.26A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$	$\Delta I > 0A$ $\Delta V > 0V$

Problem in voltage & current

ΔI

ΔV

Partial shading;
Ground fault;
Line to line fault;
Ageing; MPPT Error

Problem in voltage

ΔI

ΔV

Short circuit of one or more than one module/
By-pass diode/
Connection faults

Polycristallines	Amorphous
2011-2012: $\Delta I > 1.88A$ $\Delta V > 13.91V$ $\Delta I = [0; 1.88]A$ 2013: $\Delta V > 13.91V$	2011: $\Delta I > 2.88A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$ 2012-2013-2014-2015-2016: $\Delta I = [0; 2.88]A$ $\Delta V > 14.6V$

As can be seen in the table above, we have quite different results because we have different thresholds, but we can know how much we have deviations of current and voltage.

As can be seen, we have partial shading fault almost all the time, which explains the reasons why the data points exceed the thresholds established.

c) Summary and validation of the results

Due to the important negative impact of a PV module failure on the final energy production, we developed a method to detect and diagnose faults on PV systems based on the DC side of the PV system. The developed procedure provides us information about when the system is in a constant energy loss (faulty operation).

The approach was developed and validated using field measurements from a PV system located in IUT Cachan that have been previously described (in chapter 3). It has a fairly low degree of complexity, but it is able to cope with abnormalities present in real-life measurements.

The following types of faults have been identified in the PV system: Inverter disconnection (grid failure) and partial shadowing operation.

3. Verification of the proposed faults Detection Method at DC & AC side

The simply comparing the measured data without injecting defaults and the modeled data will not provide meaningful results about detection of faults, since it may correspond to the expected case during normal operation.

These properties motivate the injection of faults in the available measurements of power, current and voltage at the DC and AC side to detect faults reliably. The approach taken in this study is to compare differences between solar panels outputs and large differences indicate that a fault has been discovered.

As faults are occurring at some point in time and as we don't have enough data in 2013, 2014 and 2015, it could be insufficient to make analysis and to make the difference between normal and defective behavior. Therefore the test has been implemented in 2011 (9 months) for poly and 2016 for Amorphous (9 months) that have valid point of data. For **poly** during the year 2011, the measurements were taken from April 6th to December 2011. After filtering the period of low sun ($G < 200W/m^2$), we have measurements from May, 10 to December 29, 2011.

For **amorphous** during the year 2016, the measurements were taken from the 1st January to October 6, 2016. After filtering the period of low sun ($G < 200W/m^2$), we have measurements from January 4 to October 6, 2016.

a) Important notions and Selection of studied fault:

Before beginning to describe the methodology and the simulations, there are some very important notions that need to be explained since all of them will be mentioned very frequently throughout this chapter.

The most common failures of PV module failure are: String problems, short-circuited/Open-circuited modules, total blackout and shading. When an open circuit appears in one string of the PV array the whole string is disconnected and then the output current of the PV array is reduced. On the other hand, when a short circuit appears in one PV module of a string of the PV array, that PV module is disconnected and the output voltage of the PV array is reduced [25][33][48].

A PV array is formed by connection of a number of strings connected in parallel and having a number of PV modules connected in series per string. $I_{sc,a}$ is the short circuit current of the PV array and $V_{oc,a}$ the open circuit voltage of the PV array. The values of $I_{sc,a}$ and $V_{oc,a}$ are always referred to the free fault operation of the PV system while V_{mpp} and I_{mpp} may vary accordingly to the operation conditions of the system. The operation of the system may be fault free or a faulty operation.

Firstly, the thresholds that confirm a fault-free operation of the system must be fixed depending on the specific characteristics of the PV array, mainly the configuration of series and parallel connection of the PV modules forming part of the array.

Case of study: Short-circuited PV modules

In the proposed method the main focus of our work is on short-circuited modules because we only have one string (for each technology) and the modules are connected in series in each string.

b) Simulation of PV plant with faulty state (short-circuited modules)

The test is carried out using the hourly averaged data based on the fault-free operation data described previously and based on faulty state (short-circuited module) that we inject on data to analyse the new current and voltage indicators during the year 2011 for poly and 2016 for amorphous.

As said before, when a short-circuit appears in one PV module of a string of the PV array, that PV module is disconnected and the output voltage of the PV array is reduced, hence the power is reduced[48]:

$$P_{ac,meas,f} = P_{ac,meas} * \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_{mod,s}}\right); \quad V_{dc,meas,f} = V_{dc,meas} * \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_{mod,s}}\right); \quad I_{dc,meas,f} = I_{dc,meas} = \frac{P_{ac,meas}/\eta_{inv}}{V_{dc,meas}}$$

c) Implementation of the faults diagnosis algorithms to the faulty measurements

The implementation of faults diagnosis algorithms has been achieved by working under the assumption that one short-circuit panel occurs.

At AC side:

We have verified the fault detection algorithms at AC side with faulty measurements (Short-circuited modules). The tables below 32-33-34 present the results obtained from the two faults detections algorithms at AC side using the 3 models.

Table32: Results of faults detection algorithms at AC side using SDM-5parameters Model during faulty state

SDM-5 parameters extracted			
Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous 2016	
Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)
Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation

Table 33: Results of faults detection algorithms at AC side using Evans Model during faulty state

Evans Model			
Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous 2016	
Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)
Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation

Table34: Results of faults detection algorithms at AC side using PVUSA Model during faulty state

PVUSA Model			
Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous 2016	
Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)	Algorithm1 (Power Ratio)	Algorithm 2 (Power Error)
Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation	Faulty operation

As can be seen in table 26-27-28, we had “faulty operation “before injecting faults for the 3 models. The tables above show that the algorithms still emit an alarm of “faulty operation” even after the injection of “one short circuit module”.

As can be seen in the figures below that the performance index and the power error exceed the thresholds established only at the beginning and the end of each year. With the first algorithm, there is no difference between the actual free fault operation and the results after simulation of short circuited module. The effect is more pronounced using the second algorithm, we can see clearly that after the simulation with faulty state, almost all the data points exceeds the limits. Therefore, we can say that the second algorithm is more accurate.

❖ The first algorithm:

❖ **The second algorithm:**

At DC side:

We have tested the fault detection & identification algorithms at DC side with faulty measurements (Short-circuited modules):

Table35: Results of faults detection & identification algorithms at DC side using SDM-5 parameters during faulty state

SDM-5 parameters extracted							
Polycrystalline 2011				Amorphous 2016			
Detection Algorithm	Identification Algorithm1	Identification Algorithm2	Identification Algorithm3	Detection Algorithm	Identification Algorithm1	Identification Algorithm2	Identification Algorithm3
Faulty operation	Partial shading; Ground fault; Line to line fault; Ageing; MPPT Error						

The algorithms still display the same results “partial shading fault “ even we simulate the data assuming that one module is short circuited. It means that the PV installation has a problem in voltage and current and we simulate only problem in voltage “short circuited modules”. Also, it’s either the impact of one module short-circuited is minimal or we didn’t choose the right thresholds. We will study the impact of short circuited module on power output and voltage output to understand.

d) Summary and validation of the results

The procedure of faults detection and identification in grid connected PV systems based on capture losses, current & voltage errors and current & voltage new indicators described in the previous sections was tested in our grid connected PV system to evaluate the capabilities of the proposed algorithms to detect whether the system has a normal behavior or if there is an abnormality in the output power, and identify which type of fault occurs.

The algorithms developed doesn’t detect and identify successfully the faults present in the system, because the definition of thresholds for power voltage and current (Th_p, Th_v, Th_c) and the boundaries based on standard deviations must be adapted to our PV systems, which is not provided by the manufacturer. The relative error for measures and models was only taken from the specifications required by the IEC 61724 standard [46][47]. These values are recommended to ensure a correct diagnosis and reduce the probability of false faults detected. Therefore, the proposed algorithms are simple and could detect the main faults of a PV systems if we know the right thresholds to establish.

A limitation of the test of identification algorithms is that it can only be obtained using electrical model at each point in time, because Evans Model and Empirical Model don’t deliver the current and the voltage at DC side.

4. Impact of short circuited modules on the output power:

a) The performance ratio:

The PR evaluates the efficiency of the PV system by comparing its real performance to the ideal performance at STC. The ideal performance is represented by the rated DC power output of the system $P_{mpp,STC}$, while the real performance is calculated using the system’s output over a specified period of time and the amount of sunlight received over the same time period. **The PR** is calculated as follows [39]: $PR = \frac{\eta_{installation}}{\eta_{STC}}$

The efficiency of a PV system can be grouped into PV module efficiency and inverter efficiency. The module efficiency is based on the DC power output while the system efficiency is a function of the AC power output.

The system/installation efficiency (%) is given as [30]: $\eta_{installation} = \eta_{PV}\eta_{inv}$; $\eta_{STC} = \frac{N_{mod} * P_{mpp,STC}}{G_{STC} * S_{Tot}}$

The PV module efficiency (%) and **the inverter efficiency (%)** are given as [30]: $\eta_{PV} = \frac{\sum_{year} P_{ac} * t}{(\sum_{year} G * t) * S_{Tot}}$

and $\eta_{inv} = \frac{\sum_{year} P_{ac} * t}{\sum_{year} P_{dc} * t}$ Hence, the PR is determined by: $PR = \frac{\sum_{year} P_{ac} * t}{\sum_{year} G * t} * \frac{G_{STC}}{P_{mpp,STC} * N_{mod}}$

where : $\sum_{year} P_{ac} * t$ is the AC energy produced (Wh) over the time interval for which the PR is calculated and $P_{mpp,STC}$ is the DC power at STC (W) and $\sum_{year} G * t$ is the total energy received (Wh/m²) by the PV system over the interval for which the PR is calculated.

The closer the PR value for a PV system approaches 1, the closer the system production is to its ideal, rated power production.

Table 36: Performance Ratio before & after injecting faults

Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous 2016	
PR without fault	PR with SC modules	PR without fault	PR with SC modules
0.92	0.80	0.90	0.85

Yearly PR values were calculated, and it was seen that the PR with short-circuited modules was lower than the one without faults (table 36). This is caused by the system malfunction that was injected. But as can be seen the impact is minimal.

The PR can be useful for monitoring system performance ; it does not require a model, only measured data. Although it can be used for fault detection, faults can only be detected after the time period for which the PR value is calculated; The PR value can complement the model-based method for detecting PV system faults, as the model detects faults in real time, and the PR value keeps track of the PV system performance, as it degrades over time.

b) Statistical indicators :

The tables summarizes the deviations between the measurements with faulty state and the simulated values to see the consequences for the whole year of the previously mentioned faults.

i. SDM-5parameters:

Table 37 shows the results obtained from the statistical errors when comparing between the simulated power and the measured power in fault free (the actual data without the injection of fault) and the measured power in faulty state (short-circuited module) using SDM-5parameters model.

As can be seen, for **poly-Si**, the RMAE, MAE, RMSE are 4 time higher with faulty state (RMSE= 95.14W ; MAE=80.96W) than the errors of the healthy state (RMAE=3%, MAE=20W ; RMSE=6%). The impact is however minimal for **amorphous** (RMAE without fault is around 5% and with fault around 8%).

Table37 : Statistical indicators results for each year using SDM-5 parameters Model during faulty state

Indicators	SDM-5 parameters extracted			
	Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous2016	
	Faulty-free	Short-circuited modules	Faulty-free	Short-circuited modules
Period of Simulation	Apr-->Dec	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Sep	Jan-->Sep
MAE (W)	20.01	80.96	31.59	45.86
MBE (W)	-3.06	-80.27	-4.4	-43.89
RMAE (%)	3.13	14.48	4.99	7.73
RMBE (%)	-0.48	-14.48	-0.69	-7.4
R ²	0.97	0.79	0.97	0.95
RMSE (W)	39.11	95.14	40.36	57.23
RMSE (%)	6.12	17.02	6.38	9.65
N	1147	1147	1360	1360

Figure 73: Statistical Indicators with faulty state using SDM-5parameters model

ii. Evans Model:

Table 38 presents the values of the statistical errors that calculate the deviation between the simulated power and the measured power in fault free (the actual data in healthy state) and the measured power in faulty state (short-circuited module) using Evans model.

As can be seen, for **poly-Si**, the impact is minimal ; RMAE, MAE, RMSE do not change a lot (RMSE=48% ; MAE=40W ; RMAE=6.26%). The impact is however more pronounced for **amorphous** (the errors are 2 times higher with fault than the values obtained in faulty free (RMSE=84% ; MAE=80W ; RMAE=13.31%).

Table 38: Statistical indicators results for each year using Evans Model during faulty state

Indicators	Evans Model			
	Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous2016	
	Faulty-free	Short-circuited modules	Faulty-free	Short-circuited modules
Period of Simulation	Apr-->Dec	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Sep	Jan-->Sep
MAE (W)	42.37	46.10	39.59	78.94
MBE (W)	34.57	-45.26	-39.44	-78.94
RMAE (%)	6.63	8.24	6.26	13.31
RMBE (%)	5.41	-8.09	-6.23	-13.31
R ²	0.95	0.92	0.97	0.9
RMSE (W)	53.93	57.06	47.63	84.08
RMSE (%)	8.44	10.21	7.53	14.18
N	1147	1147	1360	1360

Figure74: Statistical Indicators with faulty state using Evans model

iii. PVUSA Model:

Table 39 presents the the deviation between the simulated power and the measured power in fault free (the actual data in healthy state) and the measured power in faulty state (short-circuited module) using PVUSA model.

As can be seen, for **poly-Si**, RMAE, MAE, RMSE change a lot and the error in faulty state (**RMSE=135.28W; MAE=130W; RMAE=23.25%**) are 3 time higher than the errors in healthy state(**RMSE=63W; MAE=51W; RMAE=8%**). The impact is however minimal for **amorphous (MAE=144.36W with faults and 104.87 without fault)**.

Table 39 : Statistical indicators results for each year using PVUSA Model during faulty state

Indicators	Empirical Model			
	Polycrystalline 2011		Amorphous	
	Faulty-free	Short-circuited modules	Faulty-free	Short-circuited modules
Period of Simulation	Apr-->Dec	Apr-->Dec	Jan-->Sep	Jan-->Sep
MAE (W)	50.67	129.97	104.87	144.36
MBE (W)	-49.79	-129.63	-104.87	-144.36
RMAE (%)	7.93	23.25	16.58	24.35
RMBE (%)	-7.79	-23.19	-16.58	-24.35
R ²	0.93	0.59	0.85	0.68
RMSE (W)	62.9	135.28	109.5	148.42
RMSE (%)	9.84	24.2	17.31	25.03
N	1147	1147	1360	1360

Figure75: Statistical Indicators with faulty state using PVUSA model

The first thing we notice is that for all the models and for each technology the $P_{ac,meas}$ with short-circuited module is less than the measured one in free-fault operation, and this is the reason of more deviations. If we look at figures 73-74-75 above that represents the delivered powers, we can see that there is a clear discrepancy between the output measured and the output modeled. Therefore, short-circuited modules are responsible for a considerable amount of the system's losses.

c) Output voltage profile :

In this section will be shown how short-circuited module in a system impacts the output voltage for both technologies (poly-Si

and amorphous) during the tested period of time (2011 for poly-Si and 2016 for amorphous). The system uses a configuration of $N_{mod,s} = 18$ for amorphous and $N_{mod,s} = 8$ for poly.

Figure76: The output Voltage Profile in fault-free state &with faulty PV module for poly(left) & Amorphous(right)

A Short-circuit fault in a module has a direct impact on the output voltage of the DC side of the PV system. The green scatter is related to the measured output voltage at DC side on free fault operation and the red scatter below are the output voltage profiles related to the system working with one short-circuited module. The impact of injecting the fault was minimal for amorphous.

d) Output Power Profile :

The Figure 77 follow the some concept of $V_{dc,meas}$ faulty =f (time). The power is also impacted like the output voltage.

Figure77: The output Power Profile in fault-free state &with faulty PV module for poly(left) & Amorphous(right)

e) Voltage Ratio Profile :

The voltage ratio in free-fault operation $R_{v,o}$ and the voltage ratio in faulty operation $R_{v,scm}$ are plotted against time. As explained

before, the voltage ratio is expresses as : $R_v = \frac{V_{dc,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}} = \frac{V_{mpp,sim}}{V_{dc,meas}} = R_{v,o}$

In faulty operation (short-circuit module): $R_{v,scm} = \frac{V_{mpp,sim}}{V_{dc,meas,f}}$

We can clearly have the first evidence of the impact of a fault on voltage ratio, and the impact is always minimal for amorphous.

Figure 78 : Voltage Ratio Profile in fault-free state & with faulty PV modules for poly(left) & Amorphous(right)

f) Summary:

The figures and tables above show the evolution of the PR, the statistical errors, the voltage, the power and the voltage ratio correspondent to the short-circuited modules for the two technologies. The consequences of this fault are evident. However, the consequences of injecting the faults on amorphous were so minimal.

5. Conclusion of the faults diagnosis Method:

In this section we have proposed some algorithms for automatic diagnosis of main faults in PV systems leading to power losses.

The two faults detection algorithms at AC side are based on the power ratio and the power errors. The fault detection algorithm at DC side is based on capture losses which is based on energy yields; and the 3 faults identification algorithms are based on the evaluation of current and voltage errors and indicators. The thresholds for these indicators have been established: If the values remain inside the predefined threshold, then it is considered as PV system is normally operating, otherwise it is considered that an abnormality is present in the system.

Then, these algorithms were tested by focusing on the fault “Short-circuited module” because each technology is installed in one string containing modules connected in series.

It was concluded that we need the correct thresholds so that the algorithms could properly work as we expected. Specific threshold value for PV array is essential. It avoids chances of false or missed faults detection. Therefore, we can't draw conclusions about the relevance of these algorithms. Sadly, we were not able to experimentally validate a case when short-circuited module would occur at the same time because we did not have the actual data of that fault situation. We don't have the measured I-V & P-V curves.

With these simulations we also concluded that the bigger the PV system, the lower is the impact of a fault on the output power of the PV system: The impact of injecting the fault was minimal for amorphous (16 panels) comparing to poly (8 panels).

In conclusion it can be said that algorithms give a wide range of possibilities but also bring a new set of problems in choosing parameters. Future research remains into developing methods for choosing parameters based on available datasets; and to generalize and extend these algorithms to more types of faults.

Chapter 6: Final Conclusions and Future work

In this chapter we will make the final remarks about the work done in this report. We will also discuss what follow-up work could be done.

1. Meeting the goals and final conclusions:

The present study investigates the performance of two solar technologies placed on the roof of the building IUT in the area of Cachan, France. The system is equipped with 16 amorphous modules, 8 polycrystallines modules, 2 inverters and 2 dataloggers. The atmospheric and electrical data, were acquired from 2011 to 2016, for both technologies.

A detailed procedure of data analysis, PV panels modeling and automatic faults diagnosis methods were studied using the same environment MATLAB. The simulation results were presented both analytically and graphically.

Before starting our work, there is a chapter1 presenting the scope and the objectives of this master's thesis. Then, chapter2 consists of a literature study. This provides a deeper understanding of the grid-connected and monitored PV systems, and provide a background of the methods of PV panel modeling and fault diagnosis methods in PV system.

Then chapter 3 concerns system description and data analysis with a large set of data measurements being observed. The first problem is to import, recover, visualize, process, filter and average the data referring to our systems over time. We have also discussed how we dealt with the effects of unavailable set of measurements.

The second problem concerns the modelization of the PV power output. Different models were used based on conditions and certain assumptions. An analysis of the method adopted to extract the parameters was presented along. This is done by implementing a simulation framework, which is discussed in detail in the PV panel modeling chapter. Generally a good agreement was found between the simulated results and the values found in bibliography or datasheets.

Finally the third problem is to implement automatic diagnosis method to detect and identify all significant faults over a certain threshold at AC & DC side. Here different algorithms were applied. First, the modeled AC production was compared to real-time measurements by statistical indicators using the 3 models developed. These indicators display information about the system's performance, as they calculate the deviation between the output powers, and hence detect faulty operation when significant deviations are observed. An analysis of the deviations was presented over the period of study and for different seasons. We also studied the effect of temperature and irradiance on these deviations. Finally, we discussed if the models developed agree with measurements and when the deviations is more pronounced. Afterwards, 2 faults detection algorithms were proposed: one based on power ratio and the second on power error. The algorithms at AC side were implemented using the 3 models.

The second fault detection method was based on capture losses at DC side using only the electrical model (SDM-5parameters extracted). Then, 3 faults identification algorithms were proposed based on current, voltage errors and indicators.

In the end, after running our algorithms, we saw that these indicators allowed us to know if the system is in normal or faulty operation, demonstrating good performance in certain situations. Additionally, these algorithms were also programmed to run an alarm check on the correspondent indicators. The algorithms emit alarms if the system's performance over a certain period of time decrease below a certain minimum. It proved itself very useful for detecting critical faults that were heavily affecting the system's performance.

The algorithms were tested by simulating our PV system with faulty measurements. We have only one string for each technology containing modules connected in series. Hence, we made the assumption that one module is short-circuited. Based on this, we can verify our algorithms. We discussed the impact of short-circuit modules through the periods chosen for the verification of the diagnosis method.

In addition, it results in a study which can be understood in the context of current research and extended upon in the future.

2. Perspectives:

As a future perspective, we propose to study the abnormal point above & below the irradiance-power straight line due to the lags between measurements. If the lags are less than one hour, it will be reduced since our data measurements are averaged. Moreover, we can ask for DC measurements to avoid the approximations made to fit the coefficient of each model. We propose also to modelize the inverter efficiency with an approach more technical, so that we can have accurate results. The availability of DC

measurements makes possible the faults detection based on CMM at both sides (AC and DC). The fault detection algorithm based on PLA can be also implemented at both sides by using capture losses at DC side and system losses at AC side.

Another aspect that would improve the quality of the faults diagnosis algorithms would be to develop them using thresholds of our system depending on the equipment errors, since it would be easier to understand and detect some of these faults. We should also have some knowledge of faults and their effects on current/voltage/ power so that we can set thresholds and program the algorithms correctly.

Future work also includes the development of fault diagnosis rules, once the model is implemented and its accuracy and robustness is validated. The specific causes of the faults would be identified, providing operators with valuable information regarding the required corrective actions.

This study is stated to continue. It is hoped that funding will be found to continue the study further.

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